

TRANS

lighthouses

MORE THAN GREEN

Lighthouses
of transformative
nature-based solutions
for inclusive communities

Funded by
the European Union

D3.6 Local Democracy Labs

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Purpose of deliverable

This deliverable presents the outcomes and lessons from Task 3.6 of the TRANS-Lighthouses project, focused on enabling more inclusive, democratic, and context-sensitive governance of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). Task 3.6 focuses on the creation of a space to bring science to citizens and policy makers through Local Democracy Labs. To organise the local democracy labs, we used challenges and experiences from the findings of the assessment of pilot cases (task 3.2 and 3.3), the responses to mapping of participatory cultures in pilot cases (task 4.2) and the analysis of human-nature relations (task 3.5). The democracy labs aimed to support elected representatives and municipal actors in eight pilot sites in identifying, discussing, and responding to the political and institutional dilemmas that often constrain transformative environmental governance. It also served to support the consortium with understanding the political realities affecting the implementation and long-term effects of this project. It departs from the idea that local elected representatives, such as municipal councillors, in the pilot municipalities play a key role because they can bring key democratic concerns and make NBS anchored in existing democratic institutions. By bringing locally elected representatives of the citizens together with researchers of the consortium, but also of ICLD's network in 15 countries, the labs provided a space for collective reflection and action.

The purpose of D.3.6 is to document the activities carried out, and, more importantly, to synthesize what was learned through these interventions. The deliverable compiles and contextualizes the ten knowledge products developed for D3.6 and D3.7 in close collaboration with consortium members, pilot municipalities and locally elected representatives. These include policy briefs, learning cases, and animated videos that together illustrate how democratic learning - through structured engagement with political dilemmas - can strengthen the institutional embedding and social legitimacy of NBS. It highlights the insights that emerged from structured dialogues and the co-production processes, to show how these can inform future participatory approaches to NBS that are anchored in existing democratic institutions that will exist beyond the TRANS-lighthouses consortium.

The task was moved to start earlier in the project than initially planned, in order to capture political challenges at early stages, with the end date set to enable outputs that reflect the research carried out particularly in T3.2, T3.3, T4.2 and T4.4. Therefore, the focus was partly redirected from advising the TRANS-lighthouses pilot cases to transferring lessons to other local governments outside TRANS-lighthouses. This report presents the rationale beyond the outputs produced under T3.6, including the 4 policy briefs and 5 learning cases under D3.6 but also the links to the 2 animated videos under D3.7.

The structure of the report follows the dual objectives of D3.6: to demonstrate the outputs of Task 3.6 and to provide transferable insights on inclusive governance processes for use by other municipalities, policy actors, and EU-level stakeholders. It contributes to the broader TRANS-Lighthouses ambition to foster NBS that are not only ecologically effective, but also democratically grounded and socially co-owned.

Roles and objectives in relation to other work packages

Task 3.6 was designed as an interface between research, policy, and practice. While embedded in WP3 and closely connected to tasks 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5 its purpose extended beyond assessment, serving as a strategic point of engagement with elected representatives and local governments to surface the political and institutional dilemmas affecting NBS implementation. In doing so, it offered an entry point for local actors to contribute to the research process, while also translating project insights into tools, actions, and reflections grounded in political realities.

The Local Democracy Labs created a complementary pathway to the Living Knowledge Labs (WP2 and WP5) by focusing specifically on elected representatives, and the dilemmas they face in balancing legitimacy, effectiveness, and stakeholder inclusion. As such, Task 3.6 contributed to

translating theoretical insights from WP4 into applied tools and reflective cases. Several Labs and their outputs were explicitly informed by governance archetypes developed in T4.1, and the dilemmas explored were chosen in alignment with the mapping of participatory cultures and local governance contexts (T4.2).

In turn, the outputs from Task 3.6, the policy briefs and learning cases - feed into T4.3, which focuses on policy advice and practical governance guidance. Furthermore, the participatory framing of the Labs and the animated video produced under D3.7 contributed to the communication efforts under WP6, especially for tasks targeting engagement with local politicians and civil society actors not typically reached by scientific publications.

The task also served as a platform for synthesis and co-design: the questions discussed in the labs drew on findings from WP3 assessment cases (T3.2), and integrated them into policy learning and peer exchange formats to support implementation of the pilot cases in WP5 (T5.2). The dilemmas identified through bilateral dialogues and Labs informed the development of learning cases that are adaptable for use in training, peer learning, and scenario-based workshops across the TRANS-lighthouses network and beyond.

The task also serves to diffuse learning to local governments and NBS actors beyond the consortium, including on monitoring and evaluation of co-governance (from T3.2 and T3.3).

In summary, Task 3.6 played a bridging role in the project connecting local politicians (as citizens representatives) with researchers. The task, linked research on assessment and pilot cases with governance theory, and participatory tool development through grounded political engagement, based on the everyday challenges of local politicians.

Related tasks and deliverables referenced or supported:

- T3.2 (Designing and analysing the selected data base cases and knowledge sharing)
- T3.3 (Deep Research over assessment and pilot cases from TRANS-lighthouses)
- T3.4. (Understanding and analysis on co-creation for design, implementation and monitoring of NBS)
- T3.5 (Human-nature relations: behavioural and cultural meanings attached to nature)
- T4.1 and T4.2 (Framing governance archetypes and participatory cultures)
- T4.3 (Designing innovative governance systems)
- T5.1 and T5.3 (Living Knowledge(s) Labs and implementation of pilots)

Executive Summary

This deliverable synthesizes the results of Task 3.6 of the TRANS-Lighthouses project, which aimed to support more inclusive, democratic, and context-sensitive governance of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). The task centered on creating a space to engage elected representatives from eight pilot sites through structured dialogue formats—including a roundtable, bilateral exchanges, five Local Democracy Labs, and a peer-learning workshop—to identify and reflect on political and institutional dilemmas affecting NBS implementation.

Key takeaways include the value of framing NBS not as technical add-ons but as tools for solving pressing community problems; the use of policy briefs and videos to communicate the “why” and “how” of participatory governance, and the transformative power of dilemma-based learning cases to transfer knowledge between contexts. The task resulted in eleven knowledge products: four comparative policy briefs and five learning cases (D3.6), and two animated videos (D3.7). These were co-produced with pilot partners and researchers, grounded in concrete challenges raised by elected representatives, shaped by scientific inputs from across the consortium and the ICLD’s network of researchers in 15 countries.

Policy Briefs

1. Beyond Green – Why Public Participation is Needed in Nature-Based Solutions
2. Measuring that Matters: Participatory Indicators and Evaluation of NBS
3. Creative Legality: How Municipalities use Laws and Policies in the Co-Governance of Nature-Based Solutions
4. (Re)Politicising NbS towards transformative and inclusive governance

Learning Cases

5. From Bystanders to Guardians: Bringing Community into Nature-Based Solutions (Estarreja, Portugal)
6. Community-Led Composting in Monteverde: Negotiating Sustainability and Efficient Governance (Fictional place drawing on Madrid and Caceres cases)
7. Youth Engagement in Forestry in Upper Allgäu (Upper Allgäu, Germany)
8. Revitalizing Community Engagement through Cultural Heritage (Troodos, Cyprus)
9. When Children Co-Design Nature-Based Schoolyards (Barcelos, Portugal)

Animated videos

9. Stakeholder engagement in Nature-Based Solutions
10. Children, Youth and Nature-Based Solutions

Through this process, the task generated learning about the interplay between institutional constraints, participatory cultures, and political leadership, and how these influence both the governance of NBS and the uptake of research. The task also served as a meeting point between practice and science, allowing representatives to reflect on findings from other tasks and assessment cases, and for researchers to better understand the political realities shaping implementation. By surfacing the tensions between participatory ideals and political pragmatism, Task 3.6 created multiple spaces to develop a nuanced understanding of how democratic governance can be advanced in the context of NBS.

Task 3.6 drew substantially on dialogue with T3.3 (assessment & pilot cases), T3.2 (indicators) and T3.5 (nature-human relations), T4.1 and T4.2 (governance archetypes and participatory cultures). It also drew on and contributed to T5.1 and T5.3 (Living Knowledge Labs and pilot implementation), and complements T4.3 and T6.2 by producing governance-relevant, participatory outputs tailored to the needs of municipalities and policymakers.

The main report presents the objectives, methods, and synthesis of key learnings. The annex contains the eleven knowledge products in full.

SECTION 1:
Democratic participation as
political practice

1. Democratic participation as political practice

“Municipal institutions constitute the strength of free nations. Town-meetings are to liberty what primary schools are to science; they bring it within the people’s reach, they teach men how to use and how to enjoy it. A nation may establish a system of free government, but without the spirit of municipal institutions it cannot have the spirit of liberty”
Alexis de Tocqueville, 1831

1.1. Introduction

Task 3.6 Democracy labs: interfaces between science and policies created a space to bring science to citizens and policy makers departing from their own questions, challenges and priorities. The quote by the French Philosopher Tocqueville summarises the inspiration of our approach to Task 3.6 which aims to include local councillors at the centre of the democratic process, as elected representatives of citizens. To capture their practical and political challenges and to support their work through democracy labs has allowed the consortium to better respond to their needs, but also to be able to influence their work, with peer to peer exchange and inspiration from other cases that challenge their views. The deliverables of this task are the result of a dialogue between local politicians, researchers and citizens (reached by the politicians and the researchers). While the TRANS-Lighthouses project promotes inclusive governance, this task focused on the specific conditions under which elected representatives are expected to engage in and facilitate participatory processes.

In many of the pilot sites, participation was already part of existing practice, but often with limited scope or impact. Local governments were encouraged to develop more ambitious co-governance approaches, but needed to do so within formal mandates, legal frameworks, and citizens’ expectations. These conditions frequently gave rise to dilemmas: how to reconcile inclusive approaches with administrative requirements, how to navigate political opposition or participation fatigue, and how to maintain institutional legitimacy while opening up decision-making.

Such dilemmas are embedded in local political environments. These environments include historical relationships between municipalities and communities, levels of trust in public institutions, degrees of decentralisation, and the participatory culture surrounding elected office. In several sites, participation was a source of political risk; in others, it was positively received but difficult to align with existing institutional structures. In the most advanced cases, participation was mainstreamed across different political processes and municipalities were used to innovative methods. These differences allowed for a fruitful exchange and learning.

The task approached participation as a politically situated practice rather than a technical method. It introduced Local Democracy Labs and political panel debates as complementary spaces for reflection and exchange. These formats enabled elected representatives, municipal staff and researchers to articulate and analyse the political and institutional dilemmas that arise when working with co-governance of NBS.

This work generated two types of learning. First, *process-related learning*: insights into how the consortium can most effectively share knowledge among its different member groups to maximise the project’s impact. Second, *substantive learning*: lessons on inclusive governance of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), which are directly relevant for anyone aiming to implement participatory approaches. While most of our knowledge products focus on the substantive lessons, we emphasise that the process-related insights are also valuable beyond the TRANS-lighthouses consortium.

Nature-based solutions rely on a deep and functioning interplay between decision-makers, implementers and scientific experts - not to mention knowledge-holders in the affected communities - and the implementation of this task has given deep insights to how these interactions might be facilitated and improved.

This report presents the implementation and outcomes of this work and synthesizes the eleven knowledge products that were developed - five learning cases, 2 animated videos and 4 policy briefs - in direct response to the dilemmas identified. The vidoes are discussed here because of their close link to the other work in T3.6, but are also submitted as a separate deliverable D3.7. The following sections explain how the knowledge products were co-produced, what kinds of questions they address, and the learning outcomes in both categories. While this is the umbrella report of the task, the dissemination and exploitation of the knowledge products will continue.

SECTION 2:
Implementation: from
methodology to take-aways

2. Implementation: from methodology to takeaways

The implementation of Task 3.6 combined different participatory formats with embedded co-creation across the TRANS-Lighthouses project timeline. The core methodological approach, developed based on literature on policy labs, living labs and democratic innovation (see Bakici et al 2023, Rubalkala et al 2022, Dekker et al 2020) was to engage elected representatives and local governance actors in real-time reflection, co-diagnosis, and content development through consortium meetings, Local Democracy Labs, and follow-up dialogues.

2.1. Political round-table

The task was initiated through a round-table with political representatives from the TRANS-lighthouses pilot sites at the consortium meeting in Rome in February 2024, following the very first roundtable in Azores 2023. Local politicians are often busy and it is a challenge to motivate them to actively engage in meetings, however, they are excellent speakers and talking to each other at round tables helped us to engage them in self-reflection and active support for NBS. This first roundtable served both as an orientation and as a diagnostic space for surfacing governance challenges linked to co-creation of NBS. As such, it contributes to both T3.6 and T4.4. The challenge to collaborative NBS governance in the pilot area was logged, as well as their role as elected representative, the specific actors and actions required to advance toward solutions, and questions they would like researchers to help answer via TRANS-lighthouses. The common challenges determined the topic of a policy brief and a short film, aiming to support politicians in prioritizing stakeholder engagement and inclusive governance of NBS by emphasizing its political and pragmatic value.

Roundtable takeaways

Takeaways included understanding that their challenges are shared with other municipalities; representatives realised the need for peer learning, and expressed commitment to collaborative governance and to TRANS-lighthouses. There was a consensus that complex problems require multiple minds.

Key common challenges included:

- Communicate effectively with citizens (channels, messages, visualisation)
- Manage expectations
- Making benefits salient
- Facilitation between research and administrations
- Create culture of shared decisions ("citizens must be made protagonists")

Fig. 1: Political round-table in Rome, February 2024. Source: Nathalie Nunes.

2.2. Local Democracy Labs

ICLD then carried out six Local Democracy Labs (structured, facilitated dialogues between decision-makers and academic experts) with pilot cases in Brussels, Rome, Barcelos, Estarreja, Lagoa and Strovolos, departing from their individual challenges. Roskilde and Caceres Labs were tables due to lack of relevance (Roskilde has a different pilot structure without active local government) and logistical issues (Caceres). These challenges were refined from the roundtable, from bilateral dialogues and from the mapping of participatory cultures (T4.2), where respondents had been asked to submit a Lab topic. The labs provided a space (online) to bring together pilot representatives with researchers and practitioners from ICLD's network of 15 countries, focusing on the particular challenge identified. The discussants were identified by expertise and recruited on the basis of mutual interest in the research project and practical challenges. The discussions led to practical advice and best practices from similar projects, with immediate space for contextualisation and discussion about application in the context at hand with its unique challenges. Each Lab was documented, and outcomes were synthesized and shared to identify recurring patterns and context-specific strategies.

Lab	Description	Specific output
Estarreja Municipality	Estarreja's Lab focused on strategies for promoting and conserving natural values through community engagement, co-creation, and communication, addressing the challenges of stakeholder conflicts, siloed interests, and the integration of nature-based solutions in a diverse and complex environment. It injected enthusiasm, new ideas to explore - such as the practice of nudging - and illuminated connections to other cases that have gone through similar challenges.	Learning case 1, policy briefs 3 + 4
Rome II Municipality	The lab with Rome addressed how the pilot NBS can be a connecting space for university and non-university communities, and how to overcome diverse or incompatible interests between different stakeholders. It rendered recommendations of an incremental process to enable evidence-based planning; simple and straightforward participation about the benefits of NBS; and gamifying participation.	Animated video 1

Brussels City	The conversation highlighted the complexities of engaging communities in NBS, including the need to address social benefits of participating and the potential for double solutions that benefit both nature and the community. Conclusions were made to enhancing participatory processes by reducing fragmentation, leveraging existing events and explore more interaction points for this group.	Policy Brief 2+3
Lagoa Municipality	The discussion revolved around the target beneficiaries of the pilot case - identifying groups to reach, the challenges of engaging people in participatory processes and strategies to make the experience worthwhile for them. It explored the potential of partnerships with health practitioners and other actors for a holistic impact of the NBS.	Policy Brief 1
Strovolos Municipality	The discussion focused on resistance to change from both institutions and citizens. Participants highlighted political polarization, low participatory culture, and limited cross-departmental collaboration as key barriers. Citizens often demand change but hesitate to engage, expecting the municipality to take full responsibility. Comparisons with other cities illustrated how gradual engagement, storytelling, and intergenerational involvement can foster participation. While resistance to change is a significant challenge, Strovolos can build engagement by focusing on incremental successes, leveraging cultural identity, and creating shared governance structures.	Learning case 4
Barcelos Municipality	The lab explored the political, legal, and cultural hurdles in implementing nature-based solutions in schools. Key takeaways included the importance of mapping safety concerns, shifting cultural perceptions of artificial as modern, emphasizing the principles of the child's best interest and involving children in decision-making. International examples like forest kindergartens were highlighted to inspire change, with a focus on both top-down and bottom-up approaches for garnering support.	Learning case 3, Video 2, Policy brief 3

Table 1: Local Democracy Labs held within the framework of T3.6

2.3. Consortium workshops

Elected representatives came together again in peer learning workshops during subsequent consortium meetings. These engagements are part of both this task and T4.4. In Caceres (October 2024), the "Appreciative Inquiry" methodology was used to extract lessons learned and best practices from their NBS work, with the objective to cross-pollinate solutions to common challenges, and sustain motivation for stewarding collaborative NBS governance. Elected representatives had to interview each other to identify concrete actions plans in regards to the identified indicators for co-governance.

Fig 2: Francesca Morpurgo, councilwoman in Rome II Municipality, and Ari Habeshian, councillor in Strovolos, during a peer learning workshop on indicators for co-governance of NBS. Source: Ana Maria Vargas

Caceres workshops summary

Elected representatives from five pilots identified progress in the pilots and their specific role in this, and identified success factors to continue drawing on. These included:

1. Persistence and patience (political ownership)
2. Build alliances with key people for knowledge transfer (new stakeholders on board)
3. Interdepartmental cooperation (overcoming a certain hurdle such as perception of health risk)
4. Incremental progress by leveraging popular techniques (like tactical urbanism)
5. Re-framing / highlighting benefits from various perspective / adapt the message to the stakeholder (garnering support and seeing win-wins)

In a combined roundtable and workshop, each elected representative then identified concrete steps toward each indicator of collaborative governance (selected by the consortium incl the elected reps the day before). These were translated into steps toward 1) engaging underrepresented groups, 2) getting peers on board with TRL ideas, and 3) governance adaptations in order to eventually institutionalize participatory practices.

The next consortium workshops with elected representatives (Estarreja and Barcelos, May 2025) explored how political language, ideologies, and institutional commitments influence the uptake of participatory governance strategies for NBS. Building on reflections from earlier Labs and co-production activities, these sessions provided space for peers to discuss how democratic anchoring of NBS can be advanced in politically diverse and administratively constrained contexts. Elected representatives shared challenges they faced in mobilizing support for co-governance strategies, including how to justify participatory processes within tight mandates and how to frame NBS in ways that align with constituent concerns, party ideologies, or sectoral priorities. This workshop was the direct basis for Policy Brief 4 on constructive politicization of NbS..

Workshop discussions highlighted the importance of narrative framing and indicator design as tools for institutional change. Participants emphasized that technical arguments alone are often insufficient to create lasting policy shifts—political narratives, trust, and timing also matter. The interactive format of the sessions, which included future-oriented planning and exchange on real dilemmas, helped surface ways of translating shared democratic values into implementable practices. A reflective planning process enabled participants to map out feasible steps for anchoring co-governance approaches in council routines, interdepartmental processes, or legal frameworks beyond the life of the TRANS-lighthouses project.

These workshops also contributed to the final Legacy Roundtable, where political and scientific partners jointly reflected on how the project had shaped their approaches and capacities. Together, the sessions reinforced the role of elected representatives as boundary-spanners as well as strategic allies in embedding democratic governance in NBS policy and practice. These discussions enabled ideation and validation of topics for the policy briefs in an iterative process, with multiple re-starts and changes of themes as the project developed and relevance changed with the progress.

Fig 3: Legacy Roundtable with local councillors of Barcelos, Estarreja, and Brussels. Consortium Meeting in Barcelos (2025). Source: Ana Maria Vargas

Estarreja and Barcelos workshops summary

Elected representatives emphasized the value of being engaged throughout the project, not only at the outset or in dissemination, to foster relevance and ownership. It also became apparent that structured peer exchanges increase trust and foster open dialogue around politically sensitive dilemmas, especially when repeated over time. Key points that emerged included:

- NBS must be framed in relation to citizens' everyday concerns (e.g. safety, education, public health) to gain traction.
- To access a broad political support, and remain on the agenda across party lines, NBS should be framed as technical and not within a given ideology.
- Indicators must align with political realities—prioritize those addressing actual local needs and avoid off-putting terms.
- Participation is more likely to gain institutional traction when linked to existing mandates and routines such as council reporting, committee agendas, or strategic plans.
- Effective participation requires equity and realism, especially in budgeting processes where feedback loops and expectation management are critical.

There was shared agreement that embedding co-governance practices requires both political will and administrative anchoring, and that tools (e.g. briefs, videos, indicators) should be developed in such a way that they can be integrated into onboarding and planning routines.

These insights directly influenced the final versions of the previously drafted policy briefs, learning cases, and animated videos under Task 3.6.

Type	Title	Knowledge transfer
Policy Briefs	1. Beyond Green: Why Public Participation is Needed in Nature-Based Solutions	Science → practitioners incl TRL pilot cases
	2. Measuring that Matters: Participatory Indicators and Evaluation of NBS	Science → local governments
	3. Creative Legality: How Municipalities use Laws and Policies in the Co-Governance of Nature-Based Solutions	Science and pilot cases → scientists, civil society and local governments
	4. (Re)Politicising NbS towards transformative and inclusive governance	Politicians → scientists, civil society and local governments
Learning Cases	1. From Bystanders to Guardians: Bringing Community into Nature-Based Solutions	Assessment case → pilot cases/local governments
	2. Community-Led Composting in Monteverde: Negotiating Sustainability and Efficient Governance	Assessment + pilot cases → pilot cases/local governments
	3. Youth engagement in forestry issues in Upper Allgäu	Assessment case → pilot cases/practitioners
	4. Revitalizing Community Engagement through Cultural Heritage	Assessment case → pilot cases/practitioners
	5. Recreio é Natureza in Barcelos: When Children Co-Design Nature-Based Schoolyards	Pilot case → local governments and practitioners
Videos	1. Stakeholder engagement in Nature-Based Solutions	Scientists → local governments and practitioners
	2. Youth and Nature-Based Solutions	Scientists + assessment and pilot cases → local governments and practitioners

Table 2: Knowledge products developed in T3.6 and T3.7. Source: Table created by authors.

Fig 4: Round Table with elected representatives in Barcelos, Portugal, in May 2025. Source: Jorje Araujo

2.4. Co-production, dissemination and exploitation

Significant knowledge transfer has taken place during the task implementation thanks to co-creation and validation of outputs. Task 3.6 of the TRANS-Lighthouses project sought to go beyond standard knowledge dissemination by positioning local elected representatives as strategic co-producers in the development of governance tools for Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). Building on earlier mapping efforts (T4.2) and pilot and assessment cases (T3.2), the work unfolded through iterative dialogue formats including roundtables, Local Democracy Labs (LDLs), and peer to peer learning, each contributing insights and legitimacy to the development of outputs¹.

Each of the knowledge products are contextualised by their linkages to consortium activities. With this framing, we intend to convey that the development of policy briefs was inextricably interlinked with the mutually increased understanding between scientific partners and elected representatives, and the development of strategies and measures for anchoring the pilot activities in the policy environment. The co-production process for deliverables of task 3.6 go beyond the actual products, as they represent the result of challenges, dilemmas and questions identified by local government officials and politicians. The recommendations, lessons learnt and reflections in these products are the result of different dialogues between researchers and practitioners. The authors of the products are therefore only responsible for collecting these knowledges, which we claim are collectively owned by all the participants of the labs and panel discussions. .

The task intends to be followed by peer exchange between the local elected representative in TRANS-lighthouses pilot sites and peers in ICLDs network of local governments in its 15 partner countries in Eastern and Southern Africa, Eastern Europe and Latin America.

The learning cases are intended to be used in upcoming consortium meetings, and disseminated to all pilot cases for their own use or for requesting facilitated sessions. They are also to be used

¹ For more information about the methods used see <https://icld.se/en/events/localdemocracylabs/>

in activities with local governments in ICLD partner countries, for a global reach and discovery of shared challenges and strategies across contexts and continents.

We expect the widest dissemination through the animated videos, which can be shown by partners in many different outreach contexts, including presentations, social media and websites. The policy briefs are suitable for dissemination in both practitioner circles and scientific audiences, particularly those working with local governments and to bring research and practice closer together.

Figure 5: Flowchart of T3.6 activities and outputs. Source: Graphic created by authors using Lucidchart.

SECTION 3:
Policy Briefs

3. Policy Briefs

The four policy briefs developed under Task 3.6 synthesize the key governance dilemmas, institutional challenges, and practical lessons that emerged through the Local Democracy Labs, political roundtables, consortium workshops, and dialogue between researchers and municipal actors throughout the TRANS-lighthouses project. While initially conceived as direct advisory outputs for pilot municipalities, the briefs evolved during the project into transferable governance guidance for municipalities and policymakers beyond the consortium. This shift reflected both the maturation of the project's research outputs and the recognition that many of the governance dilemmas encountered were shared by municipalities working with Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) more broadly.

The policy briefs translate empirical insights and co-produced reflections into concise recommendations aimed at local governments, elected representatives, practitioners, and policy actors seeking to strengthen the democratic governance of NBS.

Together, they address recurring tensions related to stakeholder participation, monitoring and evaluation, institutional and legal constraints, and the political dimensions of NBS governance. They demonstrate that participatory governance of NBS is not merely a matter of adopting participatory methods, but requires navigating legal constraints, institutional cultures, political realities, knowledge hierarchies, and questions of legitimacy. They collectively highlight that achieving transformative and inclusive NBS governance depends on embedding participation within democratic institutions, administrative routines, and local political cultures.

Policy brief 1

The first policy brief addresses a dilemma consistently raised throughout Task 3.6: the perceived trade-off between efficiency and participation in NBS governance. During the political roundtables and Local Democracy Labs, elected representatives frequently questioned whether participatory processes justify the time, resources, and administrative effort they require—particularly in contexts where institutional mandates are narrow, resources limited, or previous engagement efforts have yielded uncertain results.

The brief responds to this concern by reframing participation not as an optional normative add-on, but as a strategic and pragmatic governance approach that can improve legitimacy, reduce implementation risks, strengthen local ownership, and generate more robust and context-sensitive outcomes. It offers practical arguments and framing strategies to help elected representatives and municipal practitioners advocate for stakeholder participation within their own institutions.

Developed in parallel with the animated video Stakeholder Engagement in Nature-Based Solutions, the brief and video together function as complementary dissemination tools: the brief providing structured policy reasoning and guidance, and the video offering concise visual messaging suitable for outreach, internal advocacy, and awareness-raising.

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2025 | Policy Brief 1

Beyond Green: Why Public Participation is Essential in Nature-Based Solutions

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Abstract
This brief highlights the importance of participatory approaches in the governance of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), offering actionable guidance on citizen engagement. Effective governance of NBS requires moving beyond surface-level consultation to meaningful collaboration, where citizens contribute to decision-making in ways that enhance the outcomes. By fostering spaces for inclusive dialogue, policymakers can harness local knowledge, increase public trust, and strengthen the effectiveness of NBS initiatives. This brief presents strategies for integrating citizen perspectives in a way that complements other governance structures and supports elected representatives in addressing democratic challenges.

About TRANS-lighthouses
The TRANS-lighthouses project explores co-creation and co-governance in nature-based solutions (NBS), to better understand how they can be socially and ecologically just.

Introduction
Nature-based solutions (NBS) hold significant potential for creating sustainable and resilient communities, but may fall short of fulfilling this without the support and acceptance of affected communities. Whether it's urban composting projects, urban corridors of biodiversity or the restoration of local ecosystems, the key to their success lies not only in the design but in ensuring the active participation of communities in every stage of their development.

Engaging communities in the design and implementation of NBS is more than a formality. Without the meaningful participation of local actors, especially marginalized groups, NBS can fail to address the specific needs of citizens, perpetuating inequalities or undermining the long-term sustainability of solutions. Meaningful public engagement ensures that solutions are tailored to local contexts, fostering ownership, trust, and long-term commitment from communities.

This brief is designed for municipal policymakers, planners, and practitioners embarking on participatory approaches to governing Nature-Based Solutions, offering practical, experience-based strategies to address common challenges encountered in the early stages of transformative initiatives for human-nature relations.

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Fig 6: Front page of Policy Brief 1. Source: Authors.

Policy brief 2

Policy Brief 2 focuses on the collaborative monitoring and evaluation of NBS, specifically through the design and use of participatory indicators. This topic emerged through dialogue between consortium researchers and municipal actors, particularly in relation to work undertaken in Task 3.2 on monitoring and evaluation frameworks for transformative NBS.

Early discussions revealed scepticism among elected representatives and practitioners regarding overly technical or abstract indicators that lacked political relevance or practical usability. In response, the policy brief reframes indicators not merely as technical measurement tools, but as political and institutional instruments that can make invisible change visible, communicate progress, strengthen accountability, and support evidence-informed decision-making.

Fig 7: Front page of Policy Brief 2. Source: Authors.

Policy brief 3

Policy Brief 3 addresses a challenge repeatedly identified across pilot cases: institutionalization. It discusses the extent to which legal, regulatory, and administrative frameworks constrain municipalities' ability to implement participatory and co-governance approaches to NBS in a way that sustains beyond project timelines. While local governments often expressed strong political will to pursue co-creation and collaborative governance, municipal actors also reported significant barriers related to rigid interpretations of planning law, procurement rules, liability concerns, budgeting procedures, and siloed administrative structures.

The brief introduces the concept of creative legality to describe how municipalities can navigate these constraints by identifying flexibility within existing legal and administrative frameworks and using formal mandates creatively and responsibly to enable innovation while remaining within the rule of law.

Drawing on examples from Barcelos, Estarreja, Brussels, Strovolos, and Cáceres, the brief demonstrates how municipalities have used reinterpretation, sequencing, pilot structures, policy mandates, and participatory governance tools to expand the practical space for co-governance. It argues that the primary barrier is often not legislation itself, but risk-averse administrative interpretation and institutional culture.

The brief offers practical recommendations for municipalities seeking to institutionalise co-governance of NBS, including strengthening legal literacy, involving legal and technical staff early in design processes, creating intermediary governance structures, and embedding co-governance in municipal routines and policy frameworks.

Fig 8: Front page of Policy Brief 3. Source: Authors.

Policy brief 4

Policy Brief 4 addresses a recurring concern from elected representatives: the risk that nature-based solutions and participatory governance practices are perceived as ideologically loaded or as part of a political agenda not universally supported. This was first noted during the roundtable in Rome and subsequently echoed in multiple Local Democracy Labs, particularly in pilot sites where opposition parties or parts of the administration viewed NBS with suspicion or perceived participation and NBS as partisan or agenda-driven.

In response, Policy Brief 4 addresses the political dimensions of NBS governance and the role of elected representatives in constructively politicising NBS processes. While earlier discussions in the project highlighted concerns that NBS and participatory governance could be perceived as ideologically loaded or politically divisive, subsequent reflection and co-production led to a more

nuanced understanding; rather than depoliticising NBS, municipalities should seek to constructively repoliticise them by making trade-offs, values, and competing interests visible and subject to democratic deliberation.

The brief argues that NBS are never politically neutral. Decisions regarding where and how NBS are implemented, who benefits, and whose knowledge counts inevitably involve normative choices and distributive consequences. Attempting to frame NBS as purely technical interventions risks obscuring these dynamics and limiting their transformative potential.

During Consortium Meeting 7, Workshop 2 and the Legacy Roundtable in Barcelos, representatives described how they adjusted their messaging to emphasize cost-efficiency, community resilience, or public health benefits, rather than normative arguments about environmental justice or citizen empowerment. This pragmatic framing was seen as critical in building cross-party or interdepartmental alliances. The policy brief draws on these practical experiences as well as scholarly literature, and offers concrete suggestions for strategically positioning participation in NBS governance. It presents examples of how different framings (economic, cultural, technical) have been used in various pilot contexts to increase acceptance and secure support.

The brief is designed for elected representatives and NBS advocates working in environments where participation or NBS face scepticism, by acknowledging the need to navigate political realities without compromising on democratic ambitions. The guidance is framed to assist municipalities in identifying locally resonant narratives that align participation with broader municipal goals and mandates. It clarifies TRANS-lighthouses' stated aim to politicise NBS, not in a partisan sense, but to increase democratic deliberation on how NBS are governed.

(Re)Politicising NbS towards transformative and inclusive governance

Isabel Ferreira¹, Franco Llobera², Joana Santos³, Ana Maria Vargas, ⁴; Clara Orstadius⁵

Highlights

1. Politicising NbS: From Awareness to Action. Politicising Nature-based Solutions (NbS) ensures they go beyond technocratic approaches and address social and ecological justice. It requires linking participation to tangible, measurable outcomes. By grounding co-creation in visible results, NbS can strengthen accountability and democratic legitimacy.

2. Beyond Experts: Why NbS Need an Ecology of Knowledges. NbS cannot rely only on expert knowledge. Local and experiential knowledge are essential for meaningful and context-sensitive solutions. Embracing diverse *knowledges* and informal participation strengthens inclusion and leads to more robust outcomes.

3. Beyond Pilot Projects: Making NbS Stick. NbS risk fading when confined to short-term projects. Embedding them in policies and administrative routines is key to ensuring durability. Linking participation to multiple mandates strengthens institutional anchoring and resilience.

4. No Trust, No Participation: The Emotional Side of NbS. Participation fails when emotions and past experiences of exclusion are ignored. Meaningful NbS governance requires building trust through listening, empathy, and careful expectation management.

5. If People Don't Understand It, They Won't Join. Complex language excludes. Using accessible, locally grounded narratives fosters inclusion, trust, and meaningful engagement in NbS processes.

Context

The capacity to politicise ecological and social justice demands sophisticated skills to amplify the critical mass about these topics. This policy brief explores these skills from the perspective of politicisation leadership by elected representatives. Politicisation is part of a multi-component *process*, including mainstreaming, fostering shared understanding, and progressively deepening critical perspectives on the relationship between policies, NbS, climate adaptation and the contemporary ecological and social crisis. It entails questioning and acknowledging the *limits* of organizational, funding, expertise and public capacity. Constructive politicisation involves acknowledging divergent values, openly debating trade-offs, and embedding NbS within democratic processes that foreground both social inclusion and ecological integrity. Constructive politicisation requires naming and addressing these risks (Mouffe, 2005).

As municipalities face compounding environmental and social challenges, NbS are increasingly adopted to manage urban and rural spaces. However, where to implement these solutions and how to distribute their

Fig 9: Front page of Policy Brief 4. Source: Authors.

SECTION 4:
Learning cases

4. Learning cases

While the policy briefs consolidate practical guidance or recommendations, the learning cases offer structured reflections on governance dilemmas encountered in specific municipal contexts. Their function is not to generalise, but to provide grounded insights that can be useful to other municipalities facing similar institutional or cultural conditions.

The learning cases are also designed as a form of serious gaming. Each case presents a role play-based workshop material, inviting readers or workshop participants to step into the shoes of a described protagonist and attempt to resolve the dilemma presented. This is followed by a comparison between the reader's solution and the one adopted in the case, enabling structured learning and critical reflection.

A central aim of the learning cases is to enable transfer of insights from assessment cases to pilot sites—not through typologies of NBS or geographic similarity, but through shared governance challenges, structural constraints, or organisational dynamics. These include questions about authority fragmentation, informal participation, interdepartmental coordination, or the framing of ecological practices within contested political or social contexts. By surfacing such patterns, the learning cases support peer learning around context-sensitive strategies.

Rather than outlining step-by-step solutions, each case illustrates how a municipality navigated a specific dilemma, what reasoning informed their choices, and what institutional tensions or openings they encountered. This allows the cases to function as reference points for internal discussion or comparison, especially where existing governance tools or models fall short. While the briefs consolidate practical guidance or recommendations, the learning cases offer structured reflections on governance dilemmas encountered in specific municipal contexts. Their function is not to generalise, but to provide grounded insights that can be useful to other municipalities facing similar institutional or cultural conditions. We aim to use the learning cases at educational activities of the different universities, the ICLD programs of local governments, and the pilot cases. The cases will be publically available and they will be spread out by the consortium members.

Learning case 1

A recurring dilemma across several TRANS-lighthouses pilots has been how to engage diverse actors - landowners, businesses, and others with a vested interest in the area - in the implementation of NBS, especially when no formal requirement or precedent for such engagement exists. This challenge often arises where ecological objectives depend on the participation of stakeholders who fall outside the direct administrative mandate of the municipality.

The Estarreja case illustrated this dilemma clearly, and presented a strategic turning point that reflects deep respect for the democratic process while also acknowledging the need for perceived benefits for all partners.

The municipality confronted the issue of how to restore a degraded wetland that spanned multiple parcels of privately owned land, with various user groups. The core challenge was not the lack of mandate, but how to build a participatory process that made sense from the stakeholders' perspective—what would make it worth their while to take part, and how could the municipality frame the process to speak to their motivations, risks, and expectations.

Rather than attempting to establish new formal structures, the municipality chose a process-oriented solution. It initiated informal dialogue and tailored outreach to individual landowners, aiming to build trust and surface shared interests. This approach allowed them to begin work under existing constraints, without losing sight of the longer-term objective of more formalised stewardship.

The learning case underscores the need to adapt participatory practices to structural and institutional conditions. It links closely to Policy Brief 1, by illustrating what political and administrative participation can require in practice. It is relevant to municipalities working with NBS on privately held land, where relationship-building must often precede or substitute for regulatory leverage.

Link to full learning case:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/10jfjFBsl_fob8G-lAKTDivltXvYFGoUlb/view?usp=sharing

Learning Case

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From Bystanders to Guardians: Bringing Community into Nature-Based Solutions

Can a community hesitant to engage become the stewards of its own landscape? This learning case explores how municipal planner Diego de la Vega can turn passive observers into active guardians of Estarreja's wetlands.

Authors: Clara Orstadius¹, Ana Maria Vargas², Eduardo Mendes³

Learning cases are structured real-world dilemmas that provide government officials with tools and reflections to navigate similar challenges, fostering critical thinking and practical problem-solving.

Introduction: Diego's dilemma to engage the community in NBS

Estarreja, a coastal town in Portugal, is struggling with biodiversity conservation mostly due to land use changes and environmental degradation. To restore nature and support both the economy and community well-being, the municipality has chosen to use Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) consisting of different restoration trails. However, for these solutions to truly work, they need to be designed and carried out with the involvement of local people, farmers, industries, and environmental groups.

This is where Diego de la Vega, a municipal planner and biologist, faces a challenge. Many residents and key groups do not trust the authorities and are reluctant to participate in environmental projects. Some feel disconnected from decision-making.

Fig. 10: Part of the front page of Learning Case 1. Source: Authors.

Learning case 2

The Monteverde case addresses a governance dilemma common to several pilot and assessment sites: how to relate to small-scale, informal or community-led NBS initiatives when planning broader or more institutionalised interventions. In particular, it focuses on tensions that arise when longstanding traditional or grassroots practices are brought into proximity with large-scale or industrial operations.

Monteverde is a fictional location, constructed by combining and abstracting core elements from the Madrid assessment case and the Cáceres pilot. This allowed the development of a focused narrative that draws attention to the most salient aspects of the governance challenge.

The central tension explored in Monteverde concerns a successful community composting initiative and its potential marginalisation or disruption in a municipal context where industrial-scale waste management is the default approach. The municipality's preference for centralised solutions, driven by efficiency and scale, contrasts with the community-led model, which demonstrates clear environmental and social value.

The case is relevant to other municipalities that encounter friction between top-down planning and bottom-up practice, and it invites reflection on how institutional actors can support community-led NBS and realise the value of grassroots initiatives.

Link to full learning case:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1vHyiooVDPsGfqameMo1thb2Ohl1qf4gd/view?usp=sharing>

Fig. 11: Part of the front page of Learning Case 2. Source: Authors.

Learning case 3

A cross-cutting concern in TRANS-lighthouses has been how to meaningfully involve youth in the governance of nature-based solutions. This was raised repeatedly in Local Democracy Labs and consortium workshops, often in the context of stewardship, norm change, and long-term legitimacy. While many sites reference youth outreach, few offer institutionalised pathways for youth influence. The Upper Allgäu case provides a grounded example of how municipalities might approach this challenge.

The Upper Allgäu example offers a process of gradual integration, institutional responsiveness, and willingness to adapt administrative routines. The municipal forestry department sought to involve young people in developing strategies for future forest use and conservation. Rather than launching a one-off consultation or symbolic outreach effort, the process involved targeted facilitation, support from educators, and time for youth participants to familiarise themselves with ecological and policy considerations. The resulting contributions were taken seriously by professionals and informed subsequent planning activities. It illustrates how youth actors can contribute substantively to sectoral governance and how such participation can reshape professional perspectives. It also demonstrates the enabling conditions that supported youth engagement in this context. It invites discussion about what counts as meaningful youth participation and how sector-specific processes, such as forestry, can be adapted to include it.

Link to full learning case:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1bdllkYrDQ4XS1llLciZpekY3Jn9crNBP/view?usp=sharing>

Learning Case

TRANS
lighthouses

Youth Engagement in Forestry in Upper Allgäu¹, Germany

How can youth engagement be deepened in rural nature-based solutions? This case follows a forester's efforts to move beyond curriculum-based forest education and foster long-term youth involvement in sustainable forestry through facilitating co-creation, partnerships, and hands-on experiences.

Authors: Clara Orstadius², Gerd Lupp³, Reviewer: Fabio Montagnino⁴

Learning cases are structured real-world dilemmas that provide government officials with tools and reflections to navigate similar challenges, fostering critical thinking and practical problem-solving.

By reading and discussing this case, participants will:

- Understand how hands-on experiences and social incentives can foster long-term stewardship.
- Reflect on strategies to move from awareness-raising to active youth leadership.
- Identify ways to create partnerships that support inclusive and motivating youth programs.

Fig. 12: Part of the front page of Learning Case 3. Source: Authors.

Learning case 4

The mapping of participatory cultures in T4.2 allowed new categorisations to emerge, from which it was possible to identify common challenges but also other cultural commonalities that could form part of the solution. The assessment case in Troodos mountains, Cyprus, is one of the cases with very low participatory culture, and where conventional outreach efforts or procedural invitations to participate first failed to generate meaningful engagement. What it displayed, on the other hand, was a culture with weight given to continuity and place-based tradition, which could be utilised as entry points for re-framing NBS in a way that resonates more directly with residents.

The case describes how a restoration initiative sought legitimacy and engagement through alignment with cultural identity rather than through new participatory formats. The framing of the work in terms of protecting intergenerational memory and cultural landscape proved effective in gaining local traction. It shows that in certain contexts, the perceived legitimacy of NBS efforts may depend less on the format of participation and more on the narratives that surround them. The socially anchored approach is necessary to fulfil the objectives of NBS to be relevant and beneficial both ecologically, socially and economically, and for that, facilitators must respect and levy culture and tradition.

The case also encourages NBS advocates to go beyond geographical similarities to look for precedents and best practices to learn from, and to look for places with similar social fabrics.

Link to full learning case:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/15O4egO4FNoYlfK6cYdZrWDHa-GQjJZM/view?usp=sharing>

Learning Case

Revitalizing Community Engagement through Cultural Heritage in the Troodos Mountains¹

How can cultural heritage and emotional ties to a place revitalize stalled participation in the co-governance of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS)? Set in the terraced landscapes of the Troodos Mountains, Cyprus, this case follows a landscape planner's effort to shift from technical restoration to culturally grounded engagement. It invites reflection on how local identity, traditional knowledge, and informal networks can support inclusive environmental governance, especially in rural areas where formal participation is weak but attachment to land remains strong.

Authors: Clara Orstadius², Georgios Artopoulos³, Reviewer: Ana Maria Vargas⁴

Learning cases are structured real-world dilemmas that provide government officials with tools and reflections to navigate similar challenges, fostering critical thinking and practical problem-solving.

Learning objectives

- Understand how cultural framing and emotional attachment to place can support participatory governance in NBS.
- Explore how traditional knowledge holders and informal networks can strengthen stalled community engagement efforts.
- Reflect on how participatory methods can be adapted to rural contexts with low formal engagement.
- Identify transferable strategies for aligning ecological restoration with social and

Fig. 13: Part of the front page of Learning Case 4. Source: Authors.

Learning case 5

A recurring question in TRANS-lighthouses has been how to involve children and youth in governance processes in ways that go beyond symbolic participation, while remaining compatible with institutional requirements and constraints.

The Barcelos case illustrates this dilemma through a school-based NBS initiative, where students were engaged in redesigning their schoolyard as part of the "Recreio é Natureza" pilot. The core challenge was not whether to involve children, but how to structure a process where their contributions could meaningfully inform decision-making, while remaining within the constraints of public investment and technical feasibility. This required translating institutional limitations such as budget ceilings, safety regulations, and maintenance requirements into a participatory process that was both understandable and actionable for students.

The municipality and school integrated these external limitations into the co-creation process from the outset. Students were supported to develop proposals in dialogue with technical experts, gradually incorporating considerations of feasibility, prioritisation, and trade-offs. This allowed participation to move beyond idea generation toward shared responsibility for decision-making, with a sense of accomplishment and fun.

Link to full learning case:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1cgLAjafND0Ub3GV2rdwW29D2cTRE261l/view?usp=sharing>

Recreio é Natureza in Barcelos: When Children Co-Design Nature-Based Schoolyards

How can children meaningfully shape Nature-Based Solutions? This case follows a Portuguese school that invited students to redesign their schoolyard while learning to navigate budget limits, safety standards, and democratic decision-making.

Authors: Clara Orstadius¹, Andreia Coelho²

Learning cases are structured real-world dilemmas that provide government officials with tools and reflections to navigate similar challenges, fostering critical thinking and practical problem-solving.

By reading and discussing this case, participants will:

- Understand how schoolyards can become entry points for Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and democratic learning.
- Explore what happens when child-led co-creation meets municipal regulations, safety standards, and procurement systems.
- Reflect on the role of schools as spaces not only for learning about nature, but for governing with nature.

Fig. 14: Part of the front page of Learning Case 5. Source: Authors.

SECTION 5:
Animated videos

5. Animated videos

This section discusses the two videos produced under Task 3.6 for Deliverable 3.7. They are included here in addition to their own deliverable submission in order to show the connections between activities and outputs within Task 3.6.

Video 1: Stakeholder Engagement in Nature-Based Solutions

The first animated video focuses on the role of engaging the public in making governance of NBS democratic. Drawing from insights surfaced during Local Democracy Labs and political roundtables, the video communicates the value of participation not only as a normative principle but as a pragmatic necessity for the long-term success of NBS. It introduces key arguments from Policy Brief 1 in a visual, accessible format designed for use in internal meetings, public presentations, and online dissemination. By illustrating how inclusive engagement builds trust, increases legitimacy, and reduces implementation risks, the video makes a case for anchoring participation early in the policy cycle. It also reflects the framing strategies discussed by elected representatives in the consortium, emphasizing that participatory governance strengthens—not slows—effective environmental action. The video is available on the TRANS-lighthouses YouTube channel and is intended for use by consortium members and pilot sites to initiate discussions on co-governance within municipal teams and with local stakeholders.

The video is available in English language with subtitles in English, Spanish and Portuguese. In addition to nature-based solutions, this video can illustrate meaningful participation in any area, and has already during the development phase strengthened ICLD capacity building efforts in participatory democracy.

Youtube link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IP4L_WCpOk4

Fig 15: Youtube thumbnail from video 1. Artwork by Magic Markers. Source: Youtube

Video 2: Children, Youth and NBS

The second animated video highlights the importance of involving young people in the co-creation and governance of nature-based solutions, and how to make it attractive for youth to engage with nature. Building on examples from Barcelos pilot case, Upper Allgäu assessment case and Learning Case 3, the video conveys how youth engagement can deepen the legitimacy and relevance of NBS projects, and how co-learning processes - through schools, local councils, or creative initiatives - build environmental literacy and civic agency. The narrative echoes reflections from Local Democracy Labs and elected representatives, who emphasized the value of nurturing participatory habits early and creating entry points for younger voices in decision-making. The video is intended for use in municipal presentations, school partnerships, and policy dialogues where intergenerational collaboration is a priority.

Youtube link: <https://youtu.be/pqLalxkX7Hc>

Fig 16: Screenshot from video 2. Artwork by Magic Markers. Source: authors.

SECTION 6:
Main Findings and Results

6. Main Findings and Results

The work conducted under Task 3.6 focused on creating structured spaces of encounter and exchange between locally elected politicians, researchers, and practitioners. Through this work, the task captured and synthesised insights on participation and democratic governance of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), particularly in relation to the roles, dilemmas, and institutional realities faced by elected representatives and local governments. In practical terms, Task 3.6 functioned as a bridge between research and policy, translating emerging findings from the TRANS-lighthouses project into politically grounded reflection and governance guidance.

Beyond analysing participation in NBS governance, the task also developed and tested formats for reflective practice, political dialogue, and institutional learning within the consortium. Accordingly, the findings are presented in two dimensions: first, a substantive or policy dimension concerning participation and NBS governance; and second, a procedural dimension concerning the collaborative processes through which political reflection, co-production, and research-to-policy exchange were facilitated within the consortium.

6.1. Participation and NBS governance

Participation is shaped by political incentives, institutional constraints, and administrative cultures

The Local Democracy Labs created space for elected representatives to reflect on the practical and political constraints they face when supporting participatory governance of NBS. Participants consistently highlighted limited time, competing priorities, administrative capacity constraints, and uncertainty regarding political returns as barriers to ambitious participatory approaches. While many expressed normative support for participation in principle, they also noted that participation can be difficult to justify when it appears resource-intensive, slows decision-making, or introduces conflict without guaranteed implementation outcomes. In several cases, barriers were linked less to formal legal restrictions than to risk-averse administrative interpretations, siloed governance structures, and procedural routines designed for linear and technical decision-making rather than collaborative governance. This suggests that the feasibility of participation depends significantly on the institutional cultures and governance architectures within which elected representatives operate.

Trust and relational dynamics shape participation outcomes

Informal trust emerged both in case descriptions and during the Labs. In contexts where formal structures are weak or trust in institutions is low, it is often personal relationships, community credibility, or informal networks that determine whether people engage. The Troodos case (Learning Case 4) illustrates this clearly: initial engagement efforts failed until project leaders shifted their approach and mobilized cultural networks and elders with strong ties to place. The case demonstrates how trust-building may require re-framing the initiative in terms that resonate with people's identities and lived experience. This indicates that participation must be understood not only as an institutional process, but also as a relational and emotional practice. Building trust, managing expectations, and creating safe spaces for dialogue are central conditions for meaningful participation, particularly in contexts where institutional trust is low or where previous engagement efforts have generated scepticism.

Democratic dilemmas are inherent in NBS governance

The learning cases and political discussions consistently revealed that decisions regarding NBS are not politically neutral. Choices about where and how NBS are implemented, whose interests are prioritised, which trade-offs are accepted, and whose knowledge is recognised involve normative and distributive questions that cannot be resolved through technical expertise alone.

The learning cases intentionally centred on difficult governance dilemmas, including tensions between ecological restoration and economic livelihoods, formal planning and informal knowledge, and long-term sustainability goals and short-term political pressures. These illustrated how NBS governance requires negotiation between competing interests and values rather than simple technical optimisation.

Participation needs political anchoring and institutional follow-up

Participants repeatedly noted that participatory processes only strengthen democratic governance when they are linked to formal mandates, institutional routines, and visible outcomes. In several learning cases, participatory activities generated ideas and expectations without corresponding institutional capacity or political commitment to act upon them. This risked undermining trust and reinforcing perceptions of tokenistic engagement.

The learning cases about Estarreja and the fictitious Monteverde, inspired by the Spanish cases, illustrate how participation often unfolds at the project level, while key decisions remain embedded in separate political, legal, or administrative arenas. Policy Brief 1, 3 and 4 suggest that participation gains credibility when integrated into broader governance systems through links to planning processes, budgeting mechanisms, reporting routines, policy mandates, and formal decision-making structures. Institutional follow-up and feedback loops are essential for implementation, but also for sustaining trust and legitimacy in participatory governance over time.

6.2. Processes of research-to-policy uptake

Co-creation increased political relevance and ownership

The co-creation of briefs, learning cases and the video script helped ensure that project results resonated with local realities and increased the chances of institutional uptake. For elected representatives, contributing to these products created a sense of ownership and relevance of the project for their own communities, increasing the likelihood of its use in local political and administrative settings.

Trust and continuity enabled deeper reflection and cross-context learning

The time and continuity allowed for this collaborative process also proved important. As relationships between scientific, practitioner, and political partners developed over time, representatives became more comfortable voicing challenges and exploring politically sensitive dilemmas. This enabled richer cross-context learning and helped surface synergies between municipalities that might not have been visible in one-off meetings. The fact that consortium members engaged directly with these reflections enabled the political realities to be captured in the development of other deliverables and research activities.

This task positioned elected representatives as co-producers of learning, which strengthened both the content and credibility of the project's outputs. We acknowledge and recognise that local politicians involved in the TRANS-lighthouses project were already committed to participation and NBS, and represent champions of local democracy. While being key for future NBS projects, we are also aware that some of these champions may feel alone in their efforts. Supporting their work with networks that can help identify common challenges and solutions is key to having more participatory and equitable NBS. None of the products of this task would have been possible without the engagement and commitment of the locally elected representatives of the pilot projects. Our deepest gratitude goes to them.

SECTION 7: Conclusions

7. Conclusions

Participation in NBS governance is shaped by dilemmas and institutional realities. It unfolds in a terrain marked by political trade-offs, citizens' preferences, institutional limitations, and competing values. Across the pilot sites, elected representatives confronted a series of recurring dilemmas—how to reconcile ecological ambitions with economic interests, how to include diverse voices without losing decision-making clarity, and how to ensure that participation leads to legitimate and actionable outcomes. In many sites local governments experienced participation fatigue, the participation of the usual suspects or simple participation as business as usual. The challenge was how to re-invent and re-think participation that would lead to equitable and fair NBS. These are conditions to be acknowledged, navigated, and integrated into the design of co-governance practices.

Task 3.6 surfaced these challenges and supported reflection on how democratic values—like transparency, inclusion, and responsiveness—can be advanced in context-sensitive and politically feasible ways. The learning cases and policy briefs illustrate that democratic participation must be anchored both in personal conviction and institutional routine, while demanding institutional, legal, political, and relational capacities that enable municipalities to move from isolated participation exercises toward embedded democratic co-governance. Without political support and administrative integration, even well-designed participatory processes risk becoming symbolic or short-lived.

Co-production within the TRANS-lighthouses consortium itself was a pathway to anchoring new practices: the co-creation of insights and outputs between elected officials, civil servants and scientists a strategy for institutional relevance. The iterative process enhanced internal learning within the consortium. Political actors were not treated as external validators, but as contributors whose insights improved the substance and relevance of the outputs. This contributes to stronger internal alignment between scientific inquiry and political realities, and helps translate academic knowledge into governance-relevant strategies.

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Appendices

Policy Brief 1 - Beyond Green: Why Public Participation is Essential in Nature-Based Solutions

Policy Brief 2 - Measuring that Matters: Participatory Indicators and Evaluation of NBS

Policy Brief 3 - How Municipalities use Laws and Policies in the Co-Governance of Nature-Based Solutions

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Learning Case 1 - From Bystanders to Guardians: Bringing Community into Nature-Based Solutions in Estarreja

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Learning Case 5 - Recreio é Natureza in Barcelos: When Children Co-Design Nature-Based Schoolyards

Beyond Green: Why Public Participation is Essential in Nature-Based Solutions

Ana Maria Vargas Falla*, Clara Orstadius**

Abstract

This brief highlights the importance of participatory approaches in the governance of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), offering actionable guidance on citizen engagement. Effective governance of NBS requires moving beyond surface-level consultation to meaningful collaboration, where citizens contribute to decision-making in ways that enhance the outcomes. By fostering spaces for inclusive dialogue, policymakers can harness local knowledge, increase public trust, and strengthen the effectiveness of NBS initiatives. This brief presents strategies for integrating citizen perspectives in a way that complements other governance structures and supports elected representatives in addressing democratic challenges

About TRANS-lighthouses

The TRANS-lighthouses project explores co-creation and co-governance in nature-based solutions (NBS), to better understand how they can be socially and ecologically just.

Introduction

Nature-based solutions (NBS) hold significant potential for creating sustainable and resilient communities, but may fall short of fulfilling this without the support and acceptance of affected communities. Whether it's urban composting projects, urban corridors of biodiversity or the restoration of local ecosystems, the key to their success lies not only in the design but in ensuring the active participation of communities in every stage of their development.

Engaging communities in the design *and* implementation of NBS is more than a formality. Without the meaningful participation of local actors, especially marginalized groups, NBS can fail to address the specific needs of citizens, perpetuating inequalities or undermining the long-term sustainability of solutions. Meaningful public engagement ensures that solutions are tailored to local contexts, fostering ownership, trust, and long-term commitment from communities.

This brief is designed for municipal policymakers, planners, and practitioners embarking on participatory approaches to governing Nature-Based Solutions, offering practical, experience-based strategies to address common challenges encountered in the early stages of transformative initiatives for human-nature relations.

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What is Nature-Based Solutions?

TRANS-lighthouses adopts the European Commission's definition of NBS: solutions that are inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social and economic benefits and help build resilience.

Figure 1: Elected representatives from TRANS-lighthouses pilot cases, with TRANS-lighthouses project manager. Photo: Ana Maria Vargas.

Methodology

This policy brief builds on foundational insights and participatory experiences gathered in the early stages of the TRANS-lighthouses project. Insights from Local Democracy Labs, which gathered elected representatives from six pilot sites and researchers from the global community of practice, are distilled into key policy recommendations to overcome common challenges when entering into a participatory NBS governance. The lessons learnt during 5 such labs, through structured discussions with 18 local government representatives and 15 researchers, were analysed thematically and represent the core contribution of this policy brief. The recommendations are supported by other early project outputs, including reviews on governance archetypes for NBS (D4.1), mapping of governance models (D4.2), a living framework for social mobilisation and citizen engagement (D6.1), and fine-tuning of participatory methods (D6.3). These illustrative cases highlight typical challenges in participatory NBS governance. Importantly, this policy brief presents early-stage lessons from the TRANS-lighthouses project, to support continued learning across evolving NBS

contexts. While pilot cases have progressed since these insights were gathered, the participatory principles remain highly relevant for new and ongoing initiatives.

Why Policymakers Should Engage the Public in Designing NBS

Local governments - or anyone with decision-making power in creating NBS - must govern in such a way to ensure that the social, environmental and economic dimensions of a particular solution are accounted for. They may otherwise end up reproducing structures that disadvantage the already marginalised, or fail to sustain because they were not aligned with how people in the area actually live their lives. Local elected representatives should engage in dialogue with affected citizens so that NBS can better represent their needs and aspirations and foster a harmonious relation with nature. Engaging the public in the design of nature-based solutions is critical for several reasons:

Equity and inclusivity

Inclusive public engagement ensures that NBS address the needs of marginalized and vulnerable groups, ensuring that NBS do not disproportionately harm any single group or reproduce inequitable power structures. Engaging a diverse range of actors guarantees that all voices, particularly those traditionally underrepresented, are heard in decision-making. When designing NBS, decision-making actors should ask *what groups are not represented here? Why are they absent?*

Take the story of Rome II Municipality, which has an important heritage and many archeological sites. A TRANS-lighthouses pilot project consisted of creating a "green classroom" near the Sapienza University in an abandoned plot. Here citizen participation and co-creation was seen as a secondary aspect in the decision making process and the discussion tended to be about technical requirements regarding urban planning laws, permits and jurisdictions. Nature-based solutions with a component of citizen participation became central to the discussion when a municipal councillor asked about how NBS could also benefit the small businesses and schools around the university, which were absent in the original plans.

Conflict reduction and compliance

Early and continuous public involvement fosters community acceptance and can help identify and address conflicts early on, which is essential for smooth implementation without unforeseen disruptions due to stakeholders' discontent. A key question is: *How can oppositional actors benefit from the NBS?*

In Estarreja, Portugal, the city council envisioned a shift from an industrial municipality towards a more nature-oriented one, and created a project using hiking trails to foster nature tourism and environmental education. When expanding to land management and conservation, a key question was how to involve the industrial factories and farmers in this development. By putting meetings at the factory premises during lunch breaks, and inviting farmers to identify what problems land degradation caused them, they could ensure that nature-based solutions will be also tailored to these groups' needs and not infringe on their business. Creating spaces for workers to learn more about the health benefits of cleaner air and seeing them as partners could augment the potential of this NBS project.

Leveraging local and scientific knowledge

Local communities possess valuable knowledge about their environment, including historical data and unique challenges. However, they can also hold misconceptions about nature-based solutions. Leveraging local and scientific knowledge can help policymakers understand the motives behind opposition to NBS. Engagement also raises public awareness about environmental issues and the benefits of NBS, leading to better-informed citizens who are empowered to contribute to environmental stewardship. Asking stakeholders about the reasons for rejecting or accepting a particular NBS is essential in collaborative governance.

In Barcelos, Portugal, the municipality was interested in creating playgrounds more in harmony with nature, by offering space for and experiences with nature. Many teachers and parents opposed this NBS for considering it unsafe, and being conscious of their personal responsibility for the children's safety. By inquiring about the reasons for this belief, in a trusting environment, the municipality was able

to understand the misconceptions that exist about nature in early education and work together with the teachers and parents to learn about the health benefits for children of interacting with nature.

All these aspects show the interlinkages between economic interests, social realities, and environmental concerns. Particularly, it stands clear that planning solutions without the input and support of actors who live and work in that particular environment - to fit with their socioeconomic realities and culture - may not be very likely to succeed, or to sustain over time.

Local government officials and politicians should keep in mind the question "**for whom is this a solution?**".

The conceptual framework below illustrates four dimensions of NBS and how to make sure they are considered.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework: NBS lighthouses for inclusive communities. A framework for learning and unlearning across four dimensions of the TRANS-lighthouses project.

Public engagement strategies for NBS

Because nature-based solutions are as varied and diverse as the stakeholders that surround them, social mobilization takes creativity. As seen above, communities, businesses, organisations, and governing institutions have their own priorities and interests. Arguments may be based on misconceptions and biased information, or stakeholders do not feel like a certain issue concerns them. Yet, their perspectives and input are crucial for an NBS to live up to the aspiration of bringing environmental, economic and

social benefits. The following strategies can help governing bodies overcome some of the challenges that stakeholder engagement may pose in the design, development and implementation of co-governed NBS.

These are general recommendations - when designing an NBS process, engagement strategies should be tailored to each local context, with consideration to the type of governance and the level or kinds of participation embedded in the local culture¹.

Definition of NbS community (based) communication. See D 6.1.

1. Communicate the benefits effectively

Focus on the benefits of NBS. Ample efforts can be required for giving stakeholders a chance to understand what the NBS can improve, and not only what is compromised. Community mobilisation is more likely to succeed when people understand how NBS can improve their environment and address social and economic issues.

Select what to highlight. Highlighting comprehensive benefits - from cleaner air and water to job creation and social cohesion - rather than technical changes that not everyone feels concerned by, can motivate community involvement and support for NBS initiatives.

Use clear messaging. Develop clear, simple messages about the benefits of NBS, making them relatable to everyday experiences. Use positive framing to

highlight benefits such as improved public health, economic opportunities, and lively neighbourhoods where people feel connected and supported.²

2. Create inclusive platforms to leverage community knowledge and creativity

Map out key stakeholders. Systemic stakeholder identification and how they are reached is a first step in each cycle of the co-creation process.

Diversify engagement channels. Use both digital and traditional tools to reach a broad audience, ensuring accessibility for all community members, including marginalized groups. The context matters: e.g., digital tools are better suited for some audiences, while community-based storytelling is better in smaller, close-knit societies.

Host community workshops and public meetings. Organise workshops and meetings to discuss NBS projects in locations that suit the communities rather than the project staff, encouraging open dialogue and feedback from various stakeholders.

Make media campaigns: Implement campaigns using various media platforms to reach different demographics, tailor the message accordingly. And ensure they include information about how to reach you!

3. Leverage local champions

Identify and support local ambassadors who can champion NBS initiatives within their communities. These individuals can help mobilize participation and foster a sense of ownership.

Engage community leaders and local organizations to promote and support NBS projects, leveraging their influence to reach a wider audience.

4. Invite to solve problems collaboratively

Host participatory design workshops. Facilitate workshops where community members can contribute to the design and planning of NBS projects, before they are implemented. Use participatory methods to

¹ A mapping of the participatory culture, carried out in each pilot case prior to the Local Democracy Labs, was helpful in both identifying the key governance dilemmas, and tailoring the expert advice to the pilot context. Pilot case contexts were classified as cultures of either limited, partial or integral participation models, each corresponding to a governance archetype. For details, see D4.2.

³ These methods are further elaborated in D6.3 and D6.1.

ensure all voices are heard and considered.

Invest in continuous co-creation: Ensure that processes involve community members in every stage of the project, from planning to implementation and monitoring.

Clarify the preconditions. Explain the constraints and conditions that the project may be limited by or need to adhere to.³

5. Nudge (encourage) towards participation

Incentive programs. Offer tangible or intangible incentives to encourage participation in NBS projects. Incentives can include non-monetary rewards like public acknowledgment and certificates, or rewards like direct compensation, tickets for transportation, or tax breaks. It can also be highlighting the incentives inherent in participation, such as the sense of community and contribution to common good.

Make participation default. Behavioural nudging techniques to encourage sustainable behaviours and participation include making participation the default option with an opt-out mechanism – in contrast to going out of their way to participate – or leveraging social norms and peer influence to make participation desirable.

6. Continuous feedback and adaptation

Feedback mechanisms: Establish mechanisms for continuous feedback from the community, allowing for the adaptation and improvement of NBS projects based on public input.

Regular updates: Keep the community informed about the progress and outcomes of NBS projects, maintaining transparency and building trust.

Discussion questions for NBS planners

- Who, or what groups, will be affected by the planned intervention? How can we reach them on their terms?
- Who might oppose to any of the foreseen transformations? How can we engage in friendly dialogue allowing open communication and compromise?
- What are the legal, regulatory and political constraints affecting this NBS?
- What is the culture of participation in the area? What mechanisms are there to leverage?

Further reading

Deliverable 4.1 Governance archetypes framework for NBS

Deliverable 4.2 Mapping of governance models

Deliverable 6.1 Living framework on social mobilisation and citizen engagement

Deliverable 6.2. Social mobilisation and citizen Engagement

Deliverable 6.4 Fine-tuning Participatory methods

All deliverables found via www.trans-lighthouses.eu/resources

List of participants in the Local Democracy Labs

Through the discussions in the digital labs, the following people have collectively contributed the knowledge summarized in this policy brief.

- Mariana Carvalho, Councilwoman, Barcelos Municipality
- Andreia Coelho, civil servant, Barcelos Municipality
- Marta Marciel, pilot case manager, Barcelos Municipality
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Figure 2: Bioria path in Estarreja, Portugal, an assessment case in the TRANS-lighthouses project. Photo: Ana Maria Vargas

Measuring that Matters: Participatory Indicators and Evaluation of NBS

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Highlights

1. Indicators make invisible change visible

Indicators translate complex and long-term NBS impacts into tangible, communicable evidence. This enables municipalities to demonstrate progress, strengthen accountability, and build citizen trust.

2. Participation defines relevance and legitimacy

Collaboratively designed and monitored indicators ensure that evaluation reflects lived experiences, local priorities, and diverse knowledge systems, rather than only technical criteria.

3. Transformative NBS require multidimensional evaluation

Effective indicators must capture interconnected social, economic, governance, and human-nature dimensions, reflecting the systemic nature of impacts.

4. Indicators are both technical and political tools

Beyond measurement, indicators shape how problems are understood, how success is defined, and how decisions are justified and communicated.

5. Context-sensitive and adaptive approaches are essential

Indicators must be tailored to local political and cultural realities and continuously revisited through participatory processes to be meaningful and effective.

Context

"If I cannot show clear results along the way, how can I expect citizens to support these initiatives?" said a local politician from Brussels during a panel discussion on nature-based solutions (NBS).

Municipal leaders need to demonstrate the value or impact of public policies in ways that are felt by and understandable to the public. When it comes to NBS, this can be difficult, because these initiatives often bring long-term, systemic benefits that aren't immediately obvious, like improved air quality, stronger communities, or better climate resilience. Indicators can help this. When thoughtfully designed and continuously evaluated, indicators can reflect environmental outcomes, but also social equity, citizen engagement, and renewed human-nature relationships.

This brief is designed for municipal policy makers, planners, and practitioners engaged in Nature-Based Solutions with a participatory approach. We offer practical examples and guidance on how to collaboratively identify indicators and evaluate progress.

It draws on the theoretical work carried out in the TRANS-lighthouses project (task 3.3) on monitoring

and evaluation. It also incorporates insights from co-creation workshops where politicians and practitioners from the project's 8 pilot case sites were asked to choose indicators that can support their work while remaining meaningful and easy for citizens to understand.

Why indicators are important for governance performance and sustainable policies

An indicator is a way of making the invisible visible. It transforms abstract phenomena into concrete, measurable evidence. This produces information that can be shown, shared, and trusted. By combining qualitative and quantitative data, indicators turn complex issues into clear signals of change. This is especially relevant for areas where progress is not immediately obvious, such as environmental challenges.

But indicators alone do not generate transformative changes. Their impact is linked to how they are interpreted, contextualised and combined with other explanatory factors¹. It is crucial to shape the policies surrounding the NBS implementation as closely as possible to the political, social and physical reality, which requires seeking the perspectives of those affected by the NBS².

The participatory approach to indicators complements evidence-based policymaking - one of the leading governance approaches - in that authorities use data and community knowledge together to diagnose problems, guide implementation, and evaluate results. Among the advantages of evidence-based policymaking are increased confidence in decision-making, reduced implementation costs, and the ability to set priorities more clearly and effectively³. This directly reflects on the quality of government performance and the impact of public policies.

In a participatory process, jointly choosing indicators helps the co-definition of scope and purpose for the NBS implementation, and they are used to evaluate its performance during the co-creation and co-monitoring phases. They serve as tangible proof that change is happening, helping policymakers

communicate results, build trust, and make decisions with confidence.

Why implement participatory evaluation of nature-based solutions?

- To ensure the access, inclusion and permanent participation of all stakeholders, in particular those underrepresented and beyond the usual suspects
- To learn mutually considering diversity of actors and knowledge sharing.
- To support communities to identify their demands
- To inform the decision-making process within the NBS design and implementation.
- To improve the accountability strategies and make the process more transparent. The information is understood for all actors, and information on intervention goals, evaluation costs and results are available for all.
- To better uptake of findings and understanding of data collected
- To verify whether the result has been achieved and to confirm whether the intended changes and effects have been reached or not.
- To improve the accuracy and relevance of the reports by the confrontation with the participants' validation.

Policy recommendations

1. Co-design indicators through inclusive participatory processes

Designing meaningful indicators begins with listening. Before defining metrics, municipalities should engage with communities to understand who is affected, whose voices are often excluded⁴, and what outcomes matter most to different groups. For designing the inclusive process, ask, for example:

- What would make you feel welcome here?
- How could you know your voice was heard?
- What changes would show that this project is working for everyone?

Participatory processes such as community workshops, walking interviews, and informal gatherings create spaces for stakeholders to share

¹ Kabisch et al, 2016

² Van der Jagt et al, 2023

³ Cairney, 2026

⁴ Zingraff-Hamed et al, 2020

experiences, expectations, and concerns. These inputs can then be translated into indicators that reflect both qualitative perceptions (e.g. sense of inclusion⁵, trust), and quantitative measures (e.g. number and diversity of participants).

This process doesn't just apply to inclusion. It can be used to design indicators for any goal – such as improving air quality, boosting local employment, or enhancing biodiversity. For example, if the goal is cleaner air, the community might help define what “better air” means to them: fewer asthma cases, more time spent outdoors, or the smell of flowers instead of smoke. By involving people in defining what success looks like, policymakers can ensure that indicators are not only technically sound, but also socially meaningful—building trust, ownership, and long-term support for NBS initiatives.

2. Use multidimensional frameworks to capture systemic change

Transformative NBS require evaluation frameworks that go beyond single metrics or narrow categories. Evidence from TRANS-lighthouses shows that four interlinked dimensions are essential:

- **Social and cultural dimension:** accessibility, inclusion, equity
- **Economic dimension:** local opportunities, cost savings, solidarity-based economies
- **Governance dimension:** participation, influence, institutionalisation
- **Human–nature relations:** connection to ecosystems, stewardship, ecological awareness

The dimensions do not operate in isolation - they are tightly interwoven. They function like the gears of a single mechanism: when one moves, it sets the others in motion. A shift in governance can unlock social progress, which provides a fair economic opportunity, which in turn creates the conditions for sustainable natural systems. Each dimension amplifies the others, making progress a collective, reinforcing process rather than a series of separate steps.

Fig. 1 Dimensions of change.

3. Integrate indicators into governance and institutional practice

Indicators should not remain isolated monitoring tools. Their full value emerges when they are embedded into governance processes, including:

- policy design and planning,
- implementation and adaptive management,
- evaluation and reporting.

Institutionalising indicators within administrative routines helps ensure continuity, reduces reliance on individual projects, and strengthens the long-term impact of NBS. It also supports reflexivity and co-learning within municipal organisations, enabling continuous improvement of policies and practices.

4. Adapt indicator language to local political and cultural contexts

The way indicators are framed and communicated significantly affects their acceptance and use. Indicators are not neutral tools, but embedded in social and political realities.

Municipalities should:

- translate indicators into accessible, locally meaningful language,
- avoid jargon and overly technical expressions,
- and remain sensitive to political connotations of specific terms.

For example, certain concepts (such as “carbon

⁵ See policy brief 4 for a discussion on framing of NBS for wider buy-in and legitimacy

footprint”) may be politically charged in specific contexts, while alternative framings (such as “energy savings per household”) may be more widely accepted.

5. Combine quantitative and qualitative evaluation in participatory monitoring

Evaluation frameworks should integrate quantitative indicators with qualitative methods such as interviews, focus groups, and participatory validation. While quantitative data provides measurable evidence, qualitative insights are essential to capture lived experiences, interpret results, and identify unintended effects. For example, measuring physical accessibility does not fully reflect whether people feel safe or welcome using a space. Going back to the co-diagnostic phase frequently and continuously reflecting with citizens about how NBS can help to address important challenges can reduce the risks. Continuous co-monitoring allows municipalities to validate findings, identify blind spots, and adapt indicators over time. This supports more responsive and effective governance despite the additional effort required.

Evidence and Analysis

In the TRANS-lighthouses project, we encountered the challenge of creating indicators for “transformative NBS” that could be measured across different pilot cases and that provided meaningful information to the researchers as well as local politicians and communities.

A comprehensive handbook on indicators to evaluate the impact of NBS, developed by the Network of EU-funded projects (Task Force 2) within the EU Commission, was a helpful departure point⁶. As the technical and formal criteria for each suggested indicator needed adaptation to the local contexts, we discussed them and narrowed down a long list of suggestions together with local politicians across 8 pilot cases, to ensure they capture diverse knowledge systems, lived experiences, and new forms of participatory governance.

⁶<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d7d496b5-ad4e-11eb-9767-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

This collaborative work generated a structure of four key dimensions of change: (1) social, (2) economic, (3) governance, and (4) human-nature relations⁷. The following are examples of indicators for the four dimensions used in TRANS-lighthouses. Indicators are either process- or outcome-oriented, and operationalised into locally suitable questions of qualitative or quantitative nature⁸. They are evaluated jointly by researchers and municipal officials in the project consortium, with quantitative and qualitative methods including focus groups, photo voice and personal interviews. Local politicians elsewhere can use these dimensions as a starting point to adapt and localise.

Social Dimension

To answer the question if people of all backgrounds and abilities can access and benefit from the NBS. Indicators should capture both lived experiences and measurable outcomes. Quantitative indicators could track the number of access points or usage rates by different demographic groups, helping to identify and address potential social exclusion. But social dimension indicators are often difficult to quantify or describe in numbers. In the Azores pilot case, it turned out that nature trails first remained largely unused because they were perceived as unsafe to use, and hurdles still exist, such as no step-free access to the area, even when the trail itself was wheelchair friendly.

Equitable access can be a challenge even in the processes of participation. In TRANS-lighthouses, the empowerment of commonly excluded groups was seen as an important but hard-to-implement goal. Even difficult indicators are necessary - acknowledge the challenge and identify phased or creative strategies to reach underrepresented communities.

Example social/cultural dimension indicators from TRANS-lighthouses are:

1. **Creation of common goods:** What kinds of value do different groups say the NBS creates and for whom?
2. **Accessibility to different groups:** Can you easily and safely use this space? If not, what makes it difficult?

⁷ Egmore et al, 2024

⁸ Barbas et al, 2025

3. **Co-Management of NBS:** Number of community meetings and participants; number of citizen proposals implemented. Do people feel their voices actually shaped decisions?

Economic Dimension

NBS can stimulate local economic opportunities — especially those rooted in solidarity economics, such as cooperatives, community-run services, or mutual support networks. It can also support income-generating activities for vulnerable groups. Tracking the number, the type and quality of these initiatives can show how community-led economic initiatives can contribute to NBS impacts and inclusion ambition, and contribute to more inclusive and resilient local economies.

Local politicians in TRANS-lighthouses noted the importance of linking NBS indicators to the cost of living or economic opportunities. For instance, composting reduced municipal waste costs by €60 per household/year in the Cáceres pilot case.

Choose indicators that highlight economic benefits, such as reduced public service costs, job creation, or avoided infrastructure expenses. Quantitative indicators can look at the number or percentage of participants gaining income, or the number of economic activities supported by the NBS. Qualitative indicators can use examples or testimonials from community members involved in solidarity-based initiatives to measure the expected and unexpected values added by these initiatives, going beyond monetary gains and recognising non-monetary values.

Example indicators:

1. **Amount of voluntary work:** Frequency of collective work activities (clean-ups, maintenance, events). Do people feel their voluntary work is valued and recognised?
2. **Economic diversity:** Number of local small-scale or cooperative initiatives supported by NBS. Are non-market contributions (care work, subsistence practices, knowledge sharing) recognised as valuable? Number of sharing initiatives linked to the NBS (food sharing, tool library, book exchange, toy sharing, repair cafés). Do

participants feel these practices reduce economic pressure on households?

3. **Economic empowerment of marginalised groups:** Does the NBS create or protect economic space for people in informal or marginalised livelihoods? Ex. Number of street vendors, informal recyclers, or other informal workers allowed to operate in or near the NBS area. Do these groups feel the NBS supports, rather than threatens, their livelihood?

Transformative Governance Dimension

Transformative governance goes beyond formal consultation—it's about real influence. In NBS, this means creating space for citizen ideas to shape decisions and drive change. One way to measure this is by tracking how many community-generated ideas or proposals are taken up by local authorities or integrated into NBS planning.

This is about integrating project-level activities into formal governance structures - institutionalisation of both the participatory methods and the NBS themselves. The governance dimension is important for the sustainability of transformative action.

Reflexivity and co-learning is part of how municipalities should embed indicators and participatory evaluation into their institutional practice⁹.

Example indicators:

1. **Engagement of diverse actors:** Number and diversity of actors participating in the co-creation of NBS. Level of active participation (e.g., attending meetings, contributing ideas, taking leadership roles).
2. **Level of trust in decision-making:** how residents perceive their influence in decision-making, gathered through interviews or feedback sessions.
3. **Governance innovations and adoptions:** number of citizen-initiated proposals about NBS submitted and the percentage that are adopted or implemented.

The Human-Nature Relations Dimension

This dimension explores how NBS can help reshape

⁹ Kabisch et al. 2026

our relationship with nature, not just as something that serves human needs, but as something with intrinsic value. The goal is to move beyond instrumental views of nature for more relational, respectful, and inclusive connections between people and the natural world.

To assess this, indicators can look at how NBS create opportunities for meaningful interaction with nature, especially for groups who are often excluded. For example, quantitative indicators might include the number of people from marginalised groups participating in nature-based activities over time, or the accessibility of green spaces for people with disabilities. Qualitative indicators could capture how people describe their connection to nature, or whether they feel a sense of care, belonging, or stewardship.

At the same time, this dimension includes the ecological health and resilience of the natural environment itself. Indicators can track the presence of native species, biodiversity levels, or the regeneration of ecosystems. These help ensure that NBS not only benefit people, but also support conservation goals and long-term ecological sustainability.

The “use of nature” indicator was marked as a top priority by several municipalities among the TRANS-lighthouses pilots¹⁰. It captures both ecological use and social interaction with green spaces. That is a reminder for indicators to reflect how citizens interact with nature, not just how much nature is added. Access, usability, and cultural relevance matter.

Example indicators:

1. **Impact on biodiversity**¹¹: Do the plants, animals, and ecosystems around us seem healthier or more alive since this project started?
2. **Pro-environmental behaviour**: Are people doing things differently to take care of the land, water, or forests, even in small everyday ways? Number of community- led actions that restore or protect local ecosystems.
3. **Use of Nature**: Do people interact with nature in ways that feel respectful and connected, not just to take or use it?

¹⁰ during a TRANS-lighthouses workshop in May 2025 where elected representatives and scientific partners refined the indicator selection.

¹¹ also as seen and documented through the stakeholders eyes, e.g. with Bioblitz or Photovoice.

Inspired by the ladder of participation and its adaptation to NBS¹², and grounded in our work with indicators, we outline a spectrum of participation in nature-based solutions (NBS) that emphasises inclusivity, co-creation, and transformative governance. The flowchart below illustrates how different forms of engagement can strengthen both community voices and the health of ecosystems, fostering outcomes that care for people and nature together.

Final reflections

Inclusivity is at the heart of socially, economically and environmentally just nature-based solutions. For municipalities, indicators can be both technical tools and political assets that make decisions visible, defensible, and easier to communicate. Developing and evaluating them with communities turns indicators into usable guidance, to help strengthen trust, reduce risks of blind spots or unequal outcomes, and help local governments turn individual NBS projects into lasting policy momentum. As such, co-creation is political: it reveals asymmetries, amplifies under-represented voices, and helps negotiate trade-offs.

¹² Arnstein, 1969; Kiss et al., 2022.

Fig. 2: Transforming participation in NBS. Source: Ana Maria Vargas, created with AI.

Fig. 3. Measuring what matters: Four dimensions of participatory indicators for NBS

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Creative Legality: How Municipalities use Laws and Policies in the Co-Governance of Nature-Based Solutions

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Executive summary

European municipalities are increasingly expected to implement Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) through participatory and co-governance approaches. Yet local administrations often face legal, regulatory, and administrative frameworks that were designed for linear, technical decision-making rather than collaborative problem-solving. This policy brief introduces creative legality as a key mechanism through which municipalities navigate such constraints while remaining within the rule of law.

This policy brief aims to provide practical guidance for EU municipalities on how to enable and strengthen co-governance of nature-based solutions (NBS). It draws lessons from five pilot projects (Barcelos, Estarreja, Brussels, Strovolos, Cáceres) to show how local governments can adapt legal and administrative frameworks to foster collaborative governance with citizens and stakeholders.

Highlights

1. **Legal frameworks are not only constraints but potential enablers:** while some technical or risk-based rules hindered co-governance, municipalities identified flexibility within existing laws.
2. **Fragmented, siloed governance slowed down implementation,** even where legal and political support existed.
3. **Clear policy mandates (e.g. climate and water plans, EU directives)** created “policy pull” that municipalities used to legitimise co-governance.
4. **Participatory governance tools** (co-design protocols, participatory budgeting, multi-actor agreements) supported the shift toward co-governance.
5. **Institutionalising co-governance improves NBS outcomes,** enabling municipalities to move from ad-hoc consultation toward shared decision-making and long-term care.

The EU Commission defines Nature-based Solutions as:

“Solutions that are inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social and economic benefits and help build resilience. Such solutions bring more, and more diverse, nature and natural features and processes into cities, landscapes and seascapes, through locally adapted, resource-efficient and systemic interventions.”

Context

The EU increasingly promotes nature-based solutions (NBS) to address climate adaptation, biodiversity loss, and social well-being. However, transformative NBS require processes of co-governance, as their success depends on continuous collaboration between public authorities, citizens and stakeholders. During the TRANS-lighthouses project, municipalities started with a great level of interest and strong political will to test co-creation and co-governance of NBS. However, as the process unfolded, local government officials and politicians identified different institutional barriers, related to formal laws, administrative procedures and bureaucratic and political culture.

Existing laws and procedures often define narrow roles for public participation, limit flexibility in procurement, land use or budgeting, and require high levels of legal certainty that can discourage experimentation. At the same time, sectoral silos and risk-averse bureaucratic practices make cross-departmental collaboration and shared decision-making more difficult. Together, these factors can constrain the ability of municipalities to embed co-governance as a stable practice, even when there is strong interest and political support to do so.

This policy brief is based on reflections from six municipal officials and politicians from Brussels, Barcelos, and Estarreja, and a secondary analysis of self-reported results from Cáceres and Strovolos, undertaken within the EU-funded project TRANS-lighthouses.

Policy recommendations

1. Municipal level

- Use existing legal frameworks creatively and responsibly, combining formal mandates with flexible interpretation where rules are unclear.
- Involve technical and legal staff early to identify discretionary space. Bring external researchers for consultation.
- Address silo thinking through cross-departmental coordination.
- Institutionalise co-governance through concrete mechanisms, such as local charters, multi-stakeholder agreements, pilot NBS with co-decision thresholds, and participatory digital platforms.
- Embed co-governance in institutions, not as one-off participation exercises. Examples of ways to institutionalise co-governance can be to adopt a municipal co-governance charter; sign multi-stakeholder agreements; pilot small NBS with measurable co-decision thresholds; launch a digital participation platform tied to policy feedback loops.

2. National level

- Enable pilot clauses in environmental and planning law
- Support legal literacy for municipal innovation

3. EU level

- Recognise co-governance as a legitimate governance mode for NBS
- Provide interpretative guidance on flexible implementation of directives
- Fund experimentation with institutional formats
- Encourage peer learning across municipalities

Evidence and Analysis

Legal Experimentation in the Co-governance of NBS

The following examples show how municipalities use and reinterpret existing laws as spaces for experimentation, enabling co-governance of nature-based solutions without changing formal legislation. Experimenting with existing laws emerged during the pilots as officials and politicians discuss with researchers possible avenues to implement co-creation, participation and co-governance in their projects.

Barcelos: Reinterpreting safety, liability, and participation rules

In Barcelos, the renaturalisation of school playgrounds illustrates a clear case of creative legality. Government officials and local politicians described strict national rules governing school playground safety as a major institutional constraint, especially due to liability concerns when children are involved. Following these rules strictly encouraged standardised, artificial playgrounds, which conflicted with NBS ambitions. Rather than challenging the legality of the rules, municipal officials reinterpreted their scope. Conventional playgrounds were maintained to fully comply with national safety standards, while new *natural play spaces* were created alongside them. These spaces were reframed not as “playgrounds” in the technical sense, but as open natural areas for learning and play.

This interpretative move allowed the municipality to remain within the law while enabling innovation. Importantly, officials acknowledged the risks involved, especially regarding responsibility in case of accidents. To manage this tension, they relied heavily on information, participation, and shared responsibility, involving parents, researchers, teachers, health professionals, and students throughout the process.

The project evolved from a pilot into a growing network, as additional schools joined the Nature-School Network (Rede Escola-Natureza), strengthening long-term engagement with nature. It also expanded the understanding of nature beyond green spaces to include care relationships with animals through the EducaDOG Programme (Programa EducaCÃO), in which adopted shelter dogs support

students' well-being, empathy, inclusion and sense of responsibility while promoting respectful and conscious animal adoption.

Brussels: Expanding participation in technical policy domains

In Brussels, creative legality emerged in the form of informal participation practices in the technically complex domain of water management. Government officials and politicians described how working “with people, not only for people” was not institutionally standard practice, particularly for infrastructure-related issues such as flooding.

Municipal staff experimented with door-to-door engagement, neighbourhood walks, and informal exchanges. These methods were not formally codified in participation guidelines, but neither were they prohibited. Officials relied on professional judgement and context-sensitive interpretation of their mandate, noting that “nobody questioned” these practices once implemented.

The experience of innovative methods of participation expanded institutional understanding of what participation in technical domains could look like, demonstrating how creative legality can operate through tacit legitimacy and practice-based validation.

Cáceres: Legal change as a window for creative solutions

The Cáceres pilot shows how creative legality can also emerge when new legal obligations create pressure. Waste management was traditionally treated as a technical and company-driven sector, with little room for participation. However, the European Waste Directive (2018/851) and Spain's Law 7/2022 introduced mandatory separate collection and treatment of organic waste, increasing costs for small municipalities.

Within this new regulatory context, the pilot supported municipalities in adopting community-based composting as an NBS. Rather than resisting the law, actors reinterpreted compliance creatively: decentralised composting allowed municipalities to fulfil legal obligations while reducing costs. Success depended not on law alone, but on collaboration between researchers, civil society organisations, and

politically motivated local leaders willing to explore "outside the box" solutions.

Estarreja: Adapting Participatory Budgeting

In Estarreja, the municipality demonstrated a strong willingness to change course to allow citizens to fully take part in decision-making, abandoning the original project idea, which focused on classifying a Natural Park in the council. Through a public voting process, citizens instead challenged the municipality and prioritised a distributed network of biodiversity micro-reserves across all municipal areas, arguing that access and everyday connection with nature should benefit the entire population. Although this new approach implied higher costs and more complex coordination, the municipality accepted the outcome; its original proposal ranked only fourth in the vote. Participatory budgeting was essential in legitimising this shift, even though applying the formal "participatory budgeting" framework would have required additional permits and procedures. To avoid these constraints, the municipality created a "public voting of proposals," allowing participation from age 13. Citizens were then actively involved in drafting a new municipal regulation, sharing long-term responsibility for stewardship of the micro-reserves.

Strovolos: Using digital platforms to advocate for policy change

Strovolos (Nicosia, Cyprus) presents a different constellation of governance challenges. Here, regulatory entities such as the Water Development Department must be involved to ensure compliance with national policies, particularly for any field-level interventions. However, the team recognised that involving these entities too early in the process could generate "conflicts of interests," given that the same regulators ultimately grant permits for implementation. To avoid this dilemma, the pilot designed a sequential approach in which regulators participate in early

co-diagnosis, withdraw during initial co-design stages, and return later to provide technical inputs. At the same time, the conditions in Strovolos opened an innovation window: the pilot identified the potential for a digital platform that would serve as a shared space where "researchers, NGOs, policymakers, businesses, and community members can connect, share resources, and collaborate," while also functioning as a tool to "advocate for policy change."

Within the Local Knowledge Lab, stakeholders co-developed a Code of Conduct to provide an operational framework of this digital platform and to define the shared vision and principles guiding the use and stewardship of the NBS area. While not legally binding, the document serves as a collaborative commitment that supports collective responsibility and helps structure long-term co-governance.

Lessons for Municipalities: Pathways and Conditions for Co-Governance of NBS

In the pilot cases, co-governance emerges gradually, as municipalities reinterpret law and introduce governance tools over time. As shown in the figure below, municipalities shared a struggle to move beyond ad-hoc participation toward more stable, formalised arrangements in which residents and civil society organisations can meaningfully influence decisions. We argue that this requires enabling legal cultures, where legal frameworks are used in a way that supports creative solutions and co-governance, which are both essential for transformative NBS. In this section, we describe 3 pathways used by the pilot cases to start developing a legal culture that supports co-governance of NBS.

⚖️ EXISTING LEGAL FRAMEWORKS USED DIFFERENTLY OVER TIME ⚖️

Evidence from the TRANS-Lighthouses pilots shows that the main barrier to co-governance of nature-based solutions (NBS) is not always the law itself, but risk-averse administrative interpretations of legal and procedural rules. Municipalities navigated tensions between accountability and flexibility, legal certainty and responsiveness, and uniform procedures and place-based governance. Across cases, legal frameworks were found to contain under-used degrees of freedom that, when combined with participatory governance tools, enabled municipalities to move from ad-hoc participation toward institutionalised co-governance.

Pathway 1: Creating intermediary governance structures

One of the most effective pathways was the creation of intermediary structures that bridge administrations, civil society, researchers and technical expertise. Living Knowledge Labs (LKLs) emerged as key governance spaces for coordinating actors, addressing regulatory constraints, and reimagining NBS. Municipal departments responsible for planning, climate adaptation, or environmental management, use these labs as formal spaces for experimentation, learning, unlearning and alignment across sectors (de-siloing). These platforms combined co-design workshops, participatory monitoring, and collaborative knowledge production, integrating scientific and experiential knowledge to improve the legitimacy and effectiveness of NBS (Frantzeskaki et al., 2018; Raymond et al., 2017). This approach aligns with adaptive governance principles that emphasise experimentation, iteration, and collaboration in managing social-ecological systems (Folke et al., 2005).

Pathway 2: Embedding participatory budgeting in NBS implementation

A second pathway involves linking co-governance directly to budgetary decision-making. Participatory budgeting (PB) provides a semi-formal mechanism for shared decision-making over resource allocation and helps ensure that co-creation is not merely symbolic. The literature shows that PB strengthens transparency, equity, and institutional trust, while supporting adaptive and locally relevant environmental investments (Cabannes, 2004; Wampler & Avritzer, 2004; Sintomer, Herzberg & Röcke, 2008). By integrating PB into climate or sustainability planning,

municipalities can routinise co-governance and align NBS investments with community priorities.

Pathway 3: Institutionalising reflexive and continuous feedback mechanisms

Finally, pilots highlight the importance of reflexive monitoring and continuous community feedback. Co-designed ideas often encounter regulatory constraints related to land use, heritage, or sectoral regulations. Reflexive governance cycles allow municipalities to track decisions, identify constraining rules, adapt procedures, and reopen participation when needed. Digital platforms, periodic community forums, and reporting mechanisms transform participation from a one-off consultation into an ongoing civic relationship, supporting learning, trust, and shared stewardship over time.

Pathway 4. Adopting Guiding Municipal Frameworks for NBS

Across the cases, municipalities not only interpreted and used existing laws, but also adopted different types of by-laws and policy frameworks to institutionalise co-governance of nature-based solutions (NBS). One approach (Estarreja) is the creation of formal regulation for NBS, such as the creation of the network of biodiversity micro-reserves. This regulation was co-created with citizens and explicitly defined long-term stewardship roles and shared responsibilities, providing legal stability for conservation-focused NBS. A second approach (Barcelos) relies on guiding policy principles, where city councils adopt sets of NBS principles to steer design and implementation without prescribing specific measures. In this case the municipality adopted a Charter of Principles for NBS in schools and provided a small grant to the schools to enable autonomous, decentralised action. A third approach institutionalises participation itself (Brussels), through participatory architectures that combine permanent citizen bodies, temporary project-based participation, and administrative participation anchors. While different in form, all three approaches move beyond ad-hoc participation by embedding co-governance into municipal policy frameworks in ways that support continuity, flexibility, and replication.

Pathway 5. The voice of nature in the co-governance of NBS

An often overlooked dimension of co-governance of nature-based solutions is how the “voice of nature” is represented in decision-making processes. In several TRANS-lighthouses pilots, collaboration with researchers, environmental organisations and educational institutions helped make ecological processes more visible and understandable to citizens and public officials. In Barcelos, cooperation with health researchers highlighted the benefits of nature for physical and mental well-being, initially framing nature in instrumental terms. In Estarreja, students engaged directly in identifying native and invasive species and prioritising restoration actions, developing a more relational understanding of their role in supporting ecosystems. In Brussels, activities around water retention and filtration helped citizens recognise how ecological functions contribute not only to flood prevention but also to restoring urban nature. In Strovolos, local NGOs, educators and artists brought diverse perspectives to the voice of nature. Together, they shared insights on ecosystems and biodiversity, educators linked the river to community memories and intangible stories, while artists conveyed how nature “speaks” through sounds and textures, offering calmness and inspiration. In Cáceres, educational initiatives on micro-organisms and composting illustrated the importance of less visible forms of life in maintaining ecological balance.

These experiences show that co-governance can evolve from an instrumental view of nature towards recognising its relational and intrinsic value. Researchers and environmental organisations play an important role in translating ecological knowledge into accessible forms, helping to articulate nature's needs within governance processes. At the same time, young people participating in these initiatives often become active stewards and advocates, continuing to represent the interests of ecosystems in local decision-making. Strengthening these pathways can help ensure that co-governance of NBS does not only respond to societal needs, but also supports the long-term health and resilience of ecosystems themselves.

Together, these pathways show how municipalities can scale co-governance by combining legal discretion with institutional design, without requiring new legislation.

Conclusion

The evidence shows that institutionalising co-governance of nature-based solutions (NBS) is less about adopting new legislation and more about enabling legal cultures that are open to experimentation, flexible interpretation, and meaningful citizen influence. Across the cases, municipalities used existing legal frameworks in creative ways—through intermediary structures, participatory budgeting, adaptive learning, and continuous feedback—to move beyond project-based participation. This insight matters for EU priorities such as the European Green Deal, the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, and the Mission on Climate-Neutral Cities, which all rely on locally grounded NBS. Without supportive legal cultures at municipal, national and EU levels, NBS risk remaining pilots rather than durable, scalable solutions embedded in everyday governance.

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(Re)Politicising NbS towards transformative and inclusive governance

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Highlights

1. Politicising NbS: from awareness to action.

Politicising Nature-based Solutions (NbS) ensures they go beyond technocratic approaches and address social and ecological justice. It requires linking participation to tangible, measurable outcomes. By grounding co-creation in visible results, NbS can strengthen accountability and democratic legitimacy.

2. Not just experts: why NbS Need an ecology of knowledges. NbS cannot rely only on expert knowledge. Local and experiential knowledge are essential for meaningful and context-sensitive solutions. Embracing diverse knowledges and informal participation strengthens inclusion and leads to more robust outcomes.

Show less

3. Beyond pilot projects: making NbS stick. NbS risk fading when confined to short-term projects. Embedding them in policies and administrative routines is key to ensuring durability. Linking participation to multiple mandates strengthens institutional anchoring and resilience.

4. No trust, no participation: the emotional side of NbS. Participation fails when emotions and past experiences of exclusion are ignored. Meaningful NbS governance requires building trust through listening, empathy, and careful expectation management.

5. If people don't understand it, they won't join.

Complex language excludes. Using accessible, locally grounded narratives fosters inclusion, trust, and meaningful engagement in NbS processes.

Context

The capacity to politicise ecological and social justice demands sophisticated skills to amplify the critical mass about these topics. This policy brief explores these skills from the perspective of politicisation leadership by elected representatives. Politicization is part of a multi-component process, including mainstreaming, fostering shared understanding, and progressively deepening critical perspectives on the relationship between policies, NbS, climate adaptation and the contemporary ecological and social crisis. It entails questioning and acknowledging the limits of ecological, organizational, funding, expertise and public capacity. Constructive politicisation involves acknowledging divergent values, openly debating trade-offs, and embedding NBS within democratic processes that foreground both social inclusion and ecological integrity. Constructive politicisation requires naming and addressing these risks (Mouffe, 2005).

As municipalities face compounding environmental and social challenges, NbS are increasingly adopted to manage urban and rural spaces. However, where to implement these solutions and how to distribute their benefits are not decisions only scientifically or

technically based, and they are also never politically neutral (Ferreira, 2022; Ravazzi & Pomatto, 2026). Neutrality goes beyond partisan dynamics or leadership styles in decision-making. The political nuances of NbS and their transformative potential are profoundly rooted in the local participatory culture of each territory. It can be understood as the constellation of political and civic norms and values, the structuring of social hierarchies and civic leadership, and the historical trajectories shaping the sociopolitical development of municipal communities. Participatory culture is embedded within, and coexists with, a broader institutional framework of political-administrative norms and values operating at the national level within a given state and temporal context (Ferreira, et al., 2026).

Reform the model of institutional organization at intramunicipal level is a necessary step to enable the chain-flow of decisions to include ecological needs as well social needs. It requires widening the criteria and disciplinary fields to guide and access the quality of decisions from social and ecological perspectives. For the widening to happen, the levels of collaboration, cooperation and coproduction need to be adjusted, according to the local participatory culture. It requires multiple actors to recognise and critically reflect on the limits of their own roles and capacities.

This policy brief argues that rethinking the role of elected representatives in repoliticizing NbS is an important pathway to increase the resilience of municipal governance. Beyond rethinking their own role, elected representatives have the sophisticated skills to support others in the same rethinking and reposition process. Academic actors must reconsider their position in the production of knowledge, while public officers need to acknowledge the political dimensions of their technical and administrative functions. Cooperation between elected representatives, public officers, and researchers is essential for science-for-policy processes, yet it also demands a reconfiguration of their relationships and a greater openness to other forms of knowledge.

Municipalities must constructively "repoliticize" NBS by fostering genuine democratic co-production and carefully managing the emotional and relational dynamics of public encounters, achieving civic engagement without triggering partisan gridlock. In these contexts, the solution lies in a constructive politicisation co-produced by elected representatives, public officers, researchers, practitioners and organized and non organized citizens. To lead this

repoliticization process, elected representatives can guide the way to embrace agonistic pluralism, transforming dissensus into a driver of resilient solutions and enabling the emergence of new co-created imaginaries for human-nature relations.

Policy recommendations

1. Politicising NbS: From Critical Awareness to Tangible Outcomes

Politicising NbS: is essential to prevent their reduction to technocratic instruments detached from social and ecological justice (Ferreira, 2022; Ravazzi & Pomatto, 2026). Rather than producing diagnostic "paper trails" with limited impact, politicisation should foster critical awareness of whose interests, benefits, and risks are embedded in NbS decisions.

This requires moving beyond reformist approaches that create a "fallacy of action" and instead ensuring that participatory processes lead to visible, measurable outcomes. Anchoring citizen engagement in concrete results - such as improved public health, reduced environmental risks, or enhanced local livelihoods - strengthens both accountability and democratic legitimacy. In this sense, co-creation processes are not only tools for inclusion but mechanisms to deepen democracy by linking knowledge, participation, and action. By explicitly addressing trade-offs and power dynamics, politicised NbS can better respond to the root causes of socio-ecological challenges and deliver meaningful, context-sensitive transformations.

NBS and participatory processes should be embedded into permanent administrative routines (Ferreira, 2022). This reduces dependence on external funding, which can lead to unsustainable policies once funding ends (Desille & Lacroix, 2025).

2. Ecology of Knowledges: Embracing Diversity and Uncertainty in NbS Governance

NbS require moving beyond technocratic approaches that privilege expert knowledge and depoliticise decision-making. Living Knowledge Labs (LKL) demonstrate how relational environments can enable the emergence and recognition of diverse forms of knowledge, including local, experiential, and practice-based insights. An ecology of knowledges acknowledges that actors such as farmers, hunters, and landowners hold embedded ecological

knowledge that is critical to the success of NbS, even when it is not explicitly framed as political.

Constructive participation depends on legitimising this diversity and creating spaces where different perspectives can interact, including through informal modes of engagement such as walking workshops, neighbourhood assemblies, or temporary pilots. These approaches can foster trust and more authentic forms of participation.

At the same time, embracing an ecology of knowledges requires engaging with uncertainty, dissent, and trade-offs. Rather than seeking consensus through technical simplification, participatory processes should build the capacity to accommodate disagreement and adapt to evolving contexts. In doing so, NbS governance becomes more inclusive, reflexive, and responsive to the complexity of socio-ecological systems.

3. From Project Logic to Mainstreaming: Anchoring NbS in Institutional Practice

NbS often emerge as isolated, project-based initiatives, dependent on short-term funding and vulnerable to discontinuity. Moving beyond this “project logic” requires embedding NbS and participatory processes into everyday administrative routines, ensuring their durability and institutional anchoring. Mainstreaming NbS across policies, planning instruments, and organisational procedures is essential to transform them from experimental niches into sustained governance practices (Ferreira, 2022; TRANS-Lighthouses, 2024).

Institutionalisation also strengthens resilience against political and organisational shifts. When participatory processes are linked to multiple mandates and demonstrate diverse benefits - such as environmental, social, and economic gains - they become harder to reverse. This integration fosters organisational transversality and reinforces the legitimacy of NbS within municipal structures.

At the same time, local persistence and resilience plays a constructive role. By consolidating collaborative practices, shared norms, and local autonomy, it helps stabilise and defend participatory approaches against external pressures and short-term agendas. In this sense, mainstreaming is not only a technical or administrative process, but a political and relational one, requiring alignment across actors, sectors, and scales to sustain NbS governance over time.

4. Managing Emotions and Building Safe Relational Spaces in NbS Participation

The success of participatory processes in NbS depends not only on institutional design, but also on the ability to navigate emotions, expectations, and past experiences of exclusion. Participation unfolds in an “in-between” space shaped by trust, memory, and interpersonal dynamics (Verloo, 2026). Practitioners therefore need to develop interpretive listening skills to recognise underlying concerns, manage expectations, and prevent tensions from escalating into distrust.

This relational dimension is central to addressing deeper forms of institutional alienation. Building trust requires fostering cognitive, emotional, and relational capacities that enable meaningful engagement and strengthen social capital across actors and networks. Participation should not be treated as a procedural requirement, but as a demanding and ongoing process that must be carefully designed and nurtured.

Highly formalised or rigid approaches risk being perceived as superficial or tokenistic, undermining credibility and discouraging engagement. In contrast, creating safe and adaptive relational spaces - sensitive to diverse perspectives and social realities - can support more authentic participation. By acknowledging emotions and investing in relational work, NbS governance can build more resilient, inclusive, and trusted processes over time.

5. Reducing Language Complexity: Bridging Narratives in NbS Governance

Language plays a critical role in shaping participation in NbS. Bureaucratic and technocratic jargon can create barriers to inclusion, increasing learning costs and excluding non-expert participants. Reducing language complexity is therefore essential to enable broader engagement and foster procedural justice (Eckhard & Friedrich, 2025). This involves replacing abstract terminology with accessible, locally grounded language that resonates with shared values and lived experiences.

Narrative bridging is key to this process. By drawing on storytelling, cultural references, and collective imaginaries, NbS can be communicated in ways that connect diverse perspectives without relying on specialised vocabulary. This approach helps translate complex concepts into meaningful narratives that are more easily understood and debated across different

social and political contexts.

At the same time, attention must be paid to how language is received. Certain policy terms can become politically charged or associated with specific agendas, limiting their acceptance. Monitoring the clarity and accessibility of communication, particularly in participatory settings, can enhance transparency, reduce misunderstandings, and strengthen trust. By prioritising inclusive and relatable language, NbS governance can support more effective, equitable, and context-sensitive participation.

Evidence and Analysis

The learning cases from the TRANS-lighthouses reveal the inherently political aspects of NBS is. Rather than treating participation as a technical exercise, the cases show how politicising governance can strengthen democratic legitimacy without leading to polarisation.

Across the five learning cases, politicisation emerges through the recognition of competing interests, inclusion of diverse actors, and the negotiation of real-world trade-offs. In the Estarreja case, for example, the municipality faced the challenge of engaging landowners and businesses in wetland restoration without formal authority. By prioritising dialogue and aligning participation with stakeholders' interests, the process became political in the sense of negotiation and shared decision-making, rather than conflict.

Similarly, the Monteverde case highlights tensions between grassroots initiatives and institutional systems. The conflict between community composting and industrial waste management raises fundamental political questions about who controls sustainability transitions. By recognising the value of both approaches, the case illustrates how politicisation can open space for hybrid solutions instead of reinforcing divisions.

The Upper Allgäu case extends politicisation to questions of representation, showing how youth can be meaningfully included in forestry governance. This challenges traditional expert-driven decision-making and demonstrates that expanding participation can enhance legitimacy without creating conflict, provided that engagement is structured and meaningful.

In contrast, the Troodos case shows that politicisation must be adapted to context. In a setting with low

participatory culture, conventional engagement strategies failed. Instead, framing NBS in terms of cultural heritage and identity proved effective in mobilising support. This highlights the importance of narrative framing in avoiding polarisation while still making governance politically relevant.

Overall, the learning cases show that politicising governance does not mean introducing partisanship or ideological conflict. Instead, it involves making trade-offs visible, engaging stakeholders in decision-making, and aligning policies with local values and priorities. When combined with strategic framing and institutional anchoring, politicisation can strengthen democratic governance while maintaining social cohesion.

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Deliverable 3.6 Local Democracy Labs

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Further reading

Deliverable 3.6 Local Democracy Labs

All deliverables found via www.trans-lighthouses.eu/resources

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From Bystanders to Guardians: Bringing Community into Nature-Based Solutions

Can a community hesitant to engage become the stewards of its own landscape? This learning case explores how municipal planner Diego de la Vega can turn passive observers into active guardians of Estarreja's wetlands.

Authors: Clara Orstadius¹, Ana Maria Vargas², Eduardo Mendes³

Learning cases are structured real-world dilemmas that provide government officials with tools and reflections to navigate similar challenges, fostering critical thinking and practical problem-solving.

Introduction: Diego's dilemma to engage the community in NBS

Estarreja, a coastal town in Portugal, is struggling with biodiversity conservation mostly due to land use changes and environmental degradation. To restore nature and support both the economy and community well-being, the municipality has chosen to use Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) consisting of different restoration trails. However, for these solutions to truly work, they need to be designed and carried out with the involvement of local people, farmers, industries, and environmental groups.

This is where Diego de la Vega, a municipal planner and biologist, faces a challenge. Many residents and key groups do not trust the authorities and are reluctant to participate in environmental projects. Some feel disconnected from decision-making, while others are skeptical about whether these efforts will truly benefit them. Without their support, even the best-designed solutions may struggle to succeed.

Diego must find ways to bring people together, build trust, and make sure the NBS approach reflects the needs and concerns of the community. Should he focus on better

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³ Estarreja Municipality. Cover photo credit to the pilot case in Estarreja.

communication and transparency? Can small pilot projects help demonstrate real benefits and encourage participation? Or should he seek out local leaders who can bridge the gap between the government and the people? This case explores different paths Diego could take to turn passive bystanders into active stewards of their own environment.

What is the challenge here? Going Beyond Conservation

The unique wetlands and coastal ecosystems are integral to both local biodiversity and the livelihoods of Estarreja's residents. These areas, part of the Ria de Aveiro lagoon system, are home to numerous protected species and play a critical role in water regulation and flood mitigation. However, decades of industrial activity and urban expansion have significantly degraded the wetlands, leading to biodiversity loss, water quality issues, and increased vulnerability to climate impacts. The surrounding landscape includes a mix of agricultural land, small urban centers, and industrial zones, creating a complex interplay of ecological, economic, and social dynamics, which often impacts local natural habitats and biodiversity.

Diego, Estarreja's municipal planner, is leading an initiative to design Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) that address biodiversity conservation in the municipality's diverse territory. A biologist by profession, Diego feels the urgency and severity of these developments. But not all people in the area share his perspective.

- Farmers in the area are hesitant to engage, concerned that proposed changes could impose new constraints on their operations.
- Fishermen[1] reliant on the wetlands for their livelihoods fear exclusion from decision-making processes.
- The local chemical complex – a major employer – left a strong environmental liability in the council, and citizens often identify soil and water contamination, as well as air quality, as major concerns. Reduced business would weigh heavily on the community employment rate[2] [3] .
- Many residents are focused on immediate economic concerns, and less concerned with the urgency of environmental restoration.

Yet, without their input and support, measures might fail to address real needs or face resistance during implementation. Restoring ecosystems without consulting farmers could disrupt their operations, leading to unintended consequences. If farmers' and foresters' needs or fishermen's access to the wetlands are overlooked, the actors may display resistance during implementation.

Diego must reconcile these diverging perspectives to convince everyone that engaging in NBS planning is time and resources well spent. The challenge is complicated by Estarreja's governance structure, where municipal decisions must align with national biodiversity goals and funding requirements, often leaving little flexibility to adapt to local needs. Meanwhile, NGOs push for stricter measures and faster action, sometimes expressing frustration with the municipality's pace. These priorities clash with local

economic and social concerns. Diego, trained as a biologist, brings technical expertise in ecosystem restoration and biodiversity conservation and is equipped to design effective ecological solutions, but his success depends on navigating the practical realities faced by local stakeholders to ensure that proposed measures address both ecological and socio-economic priorities.

Conceptual Framework. NBS lighthouses for inclusive communities.

A framework for learning and unlearning across four dimensions of the TRANS-lighthouses project.

Diego's original proposal of NBS

The proposed Nature-Based Solution in Estarreja builds on the BioRia initiative, which promotes nature tourism and environmental education under the motto "Know it, to protect it." By enhancing the region's rich wetlands, the municipality has developed a network of eight trails with visitor infrastructure, leisure areas, and educational programs. This approach aims to restore biodiversity while fostering a deeper connection between the community and its natural environment, encouraging local stewardship and sustainable economic opportunities.

Discussion part: How can NBS better respond to socio-economic needs?

You are assigned to support the work of Diego and provide actionable solutions to both policies and practices that can help the municipality of Estarreja to overcome their challenge.

There are several things to consider. How can the proposed NBS plan (nature trails) be modified to also reflect the socio-economic and democratic concerns of the local actors? What strategies could ensure that the communities mentioned above feel included in decision-making and benefit from the project's outcomes? How can Diego build a process that balances technical expertise with community input and ensures that all voices are heard?

Imagine you are in Diego's shoes. How would you structure the engagement process?

You must balance the institutional constraints, low community trust, and limited participatory culture with the urgent need to identify and design NBS, given the degradation of biodiversity. You receive conflicting feedback from government departments, citizens, NGOs and businesses and must make strategic choices to foster engagement without alienating any group.

Guiding material: Local Democracy Toolbox

This set of principles can guide your discussion, but use also your own experience and examples from your own local government.

- **Participation** – How can more voices be included?
 - ◆ How can Diego create spaces where local residents, farmers, industries, and environmental groups feel heard and valued?
 - ◆ What methods could encourage those who are skeptical or disengaged to take part in decision-making?
 - ◆ How can local leaders, schools, or community organizations help bridge the gap between the municipality and the people?

- **Transparency** – How can trust be built through openness?
 - ◆ What information about BioRia and its benefits should be shared to address community concerns?
 - ◆ How can Diego ensure that decisions and processes are clearly communicated to all groups?
 - ◆ What tools (e.g., public meetings, social media, local newspapers) can be used to keep people informed and involved?

- **Accountability** – How can commitments be made and upheld?
 - ◆ What mechanisms can ensure that community input is reflected in decision-making?
 - ◆ How can Diego demonstrate that the municipality is following through on

- its promises?
 - ◆ What role can independent monitoring or local advisory groups play in keeping the project on track?
- **Equity** – How can benefits be fairly distributed?
- ◆ How can Diego ensure that all groups—including those with fewer resources or less political influence—benefit from BioRia?
 - ◆ What strategies can make it easier for traditionally excluded groups to participate in and benefit from the project?
 - ◆ How can economic opportunities (e.g., eco-tourism jobs, education programs) be shared fairly among community members?

Guidance on communication for social mobilization

Images and messaging: core values and commitments		
Core values	Meaning	Commitments
Respect for the dignity of people concerned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > appreciating the people and situations > showing consideration for people's privacy and dignity > regarding people as active, valuable and capable agents of change in their own lives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Authentic representation: providing truth and context when portraying the lives of individuals and communities >> Contributor-led stories and locally led content development: putting the people and communities at the centre of communications
Belief in the equality of all people	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > respecting the rights of all people > applying the same standards to everyone > promoting an appreciation of diversity > committing to non-discrimination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Informed consent: all content is obtained with the full understanding, participation and permission of those featured, or in the case of children, of their parents or guardians
Acceptance of the need to promote solidarity, fairness and justice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > <i>Solidarity:</i> using practices, images and messages that promote working together with, rather than on behalf, of communities. > <i>Fairness and justice:</i> highlighting causes, calling for actions to address them and implementing a rights-based approach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Upholding standards and Doing No Harm In planning, gathering and disseminating content - conform to the highest standards and international instruments relating to human rights - commit to the protection of people in vulnerable situations and those with specific needs

Table adapted from Dóchas Guide to Ethical Communications (2023).

Real case ending

To move forward, Diego convinced his municipal team in Estarreja to adopt a co-diagnostic approach, involving stakeholders from the outset in identifying challenges and shaping solutions for the degraded wetlands. Rather than seeking approval for pre-designed plans, they invited farmers, fishermen, foresters, residents, NGOs, governmental and research entities and the chemical complex, among others, to participate in workshops and discussions to collectively define the issues and explore potential Nature-Based Solutions (NBS). This approach helped to foster a sense of shared responsibility for the outcomes.

The team carefully framed the initiative to align with the priorities and concerns of each stakeholder group. For farmers, they emphasized how they are important in managing the territory and that collaboration may bring benefits for both the environment and their livelihoods. Foresters and farmers were engaged through discussions about how healthier ecosystems could enhance fish stocks and provide long-term benefits for their trade. For the chemical factory, the team highlighted opportunities to enhance its corporate image, align with environmental regulations, and demonstrate leadership in sustainability. Residents were shown how flood risk mitigation and eco-tourism could improve quality of life^[1] and bring economic opportunities to the community.

By demonstrating how participation in the co-diagnostic process could directly benefit each group, the team not only built trust but also encouraged active engagement. This inclusive and interest-driven framing helped to transform the perception of NBS from an abstract ecological goal to shared, practical solutions with tangible local benefits. Ultimately, the shift toward co-diagnosis and tailored communication paved the way for broader participation. This sets a better stage for agreeing on solutions to implement, as a next stage of the project.

Step out of Diego's shoes and consider the case as an observer. Do you think the stakeholders will continue actively working together? Will they find and support implementation of NBS? How should the municipality sustain the process?

Final discussion questions:

- How can planners balance the urgency of finding solutions with the time that is necessary to engage in co-diagnostics?
- How can local governments balance technical expertise (for example their understanding of biodiversity) with community knowledge and other areas of interest) in decision-making for NBS?
- What are the risks of failing to engage local stakeholders in environmental governance projects?
- What are similar challenges you experience in your own work with NBS?

Community-Led Composting in Monteverde: Negotiating Sustainability and Efficient Governance

Authors: Uray Shyta Damayanti, Clara Orstadius¹. Contributors: Monica Cuende, Franco Llobera Serra², José Luis Fernández-Pacheco³, Ana Maria Vargas⁴

Learning cases are structured real-world dilemmas that provide government officials with tools and reflections to navigate similar challenges, fostering critical thinking and practical problem-solving.

How can local governments balance regulatory responsibilities, contractual obligations, and public health concerns with the aspirations of community-led sustainability initiatives? This case offers insights into the governance of small-scale, community-driven NBS and the potential of co-production processes, involving municipalities, communities, and private actors. It invites participants to explore the tensions, risks, and transformative opportunities of multi-stakeholder governance, particularly when initiatives rely on voluntary engagement and informal partnerships.

Through this scenario, readers will:

- *Analyze the complexities of integrating traditional, low-tech composting methods into a modern urban waste management system.*
- *Evaluate the competing interests of stakeholders, including local government, private waste contractors, and community-led initiatives.*
- *Propose strategies for balancing regulatory requirements and top-down policy enforcement (typically conventional capital-intensive solutions) with community-driven sustainability efforts.*
- *Identify internal tensions that may arise in community-led sustainability initiatives and how these affect the legitimacy, equity, and long-term sustainability of Nature-Based Solutions.*

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Note: this is a fictional case inspired by and building on experiences from two assessment cases and one pilot case ([Madrid](#) and [Moisdon-la-Riviere](#) and [Caceres](#) respectively) in TRANS-lighthouses.

Case description

Monteverde, a historic town in Andalusia, Spain, is home to 10,000 residents. The city is characterized by its small-scale local economy, family-owned businesses, and tight-knit neighborhoods. Many residents have strong ties to traditional ways of living and a history of informal, community-led initiatives. It is also home to a university faculty with studies on environmental and social issues.

The local government has long relied on large-scale waste management contracts to handle the city's waste, including organic waste from markets, households, and restaurants. Local activists and small-business owners were frustrated by the growing volumes of organic waste being sent to distant landfills, contributing to environmental harm and wasting potential local resources. They also felt sidelined by the municipality's exclusive reliance on large private contractors, which left little room for community participation or small-scale economic opportunities.

The group began promoting decentralized composting as an alternative to the city's centralized waste disposal system. For many, composting was not just an environmental practice but a way to reclaim agency, reduce waste collection costs, and support local farmers by turning organic waste into valuable compost.

could take to turn passive bystanders into active stewards of their own environment.

The conflict

Robert, a sustainability advocate and local entrepreneur, took on an informal leadership position within the group. He saw an opportunity to turn organic waste into a resource. His resolve encouraged neighborhoods to establish small-scale composting sites to reduce landfill waste, enrich local soils, and promote circular urban sustainability. The project quickly gained support from local farmers, market vendors, and environmentally conscious residents who saw the economic and ecological benefits of composting. However, the initiative also ran into opposition.

Municipal authorities and private waste contractors raised concerns about the initiative's impact on the city's existing waste management policies. They raised several points of contention:

- Regulatory compliance: The city had strict waste disposal laws, and unauthorized composting sites were technically illegal.
- Contractual obligations: The municipal government had a long-term contract with a private waste management company, which viewed community composting as a threat to its business model.
- Sanitation and public health: Authorities cited potential health risks, arguing that improperly managed composting could lead to pest infestations and unpleasant odors.

From the municipality's perspective, these concerns were both legalistic and practical. City officials were under pressure to comply with public health regulations, avoid violating existing contracts, and ensure that waste management remained predictable, sanitary, and efficient. Many municipal staff recognized the potential of community composting but felt constrained by institutional responsibilities and the risk of public backlash if informal composting sites led to problems.

The dilemma

Robert now faces a difficult situation: how to convince the municipality to recognize and integrate small-scale composting into the city's waste management strategy while avoiding a complete shutdown of the initiative?

Should he:

- **Negotiate a compromise?** Work with municipal authorities to develop pilot projects that test small-scale composting within a regulated framework?
- **Mobilize public support?** Leverage community backing to push for policy changes through advocacy campaigns and petitions?
- **Seek external partnerships?** Collaborate with universities, environmental organizations, and international networks to strengthen the initiative's legitimacy?
- **Challenge the system?** Take legal action or direct protest measures to challenge the city's restrictive policies?

Discussion questions - Round 1

Put yourself in Robert's shoes and help him define the strategy forward.

- If you were Robert, which strategy would you prioritize to reduce tensions and build collaboration?
- How would you approach the municipality to gain their trust while protecting the interests of the local communities?
- What trade-offs would you be willing to accept to secure a compromise?
- How could you ensure that the community composting initiative remains sustainable and scalable in the long term?

Guiding material: The stakeholders

Local communities and small enterprises:

- Motivated by environmental and economic benefits.
- Want greater participation in urban sustainability policies.
- Feel excluded from decision-making and frustrated with bureaucratic obstacles.

Municipal government:

- Must balance sustainability goals with legal and contractual obligations.
- Concerned about maintaining order and avoiding conflicts with private contractors.
- Sees potential but fears setting a precedent that could lead to regulatory challenges.

Private waste management company:

- Holds a lucrative contract with the municipality.
- Views decentralized composting as a financial threat.
- Leverages contractual obligations to pressure the city into enforcing centralized waste policies.

Environmental organizations and researchers:

- Support the initiative as part of a broader transition to a circular economy.
- Offer scientific data and policy recommendations to address sanitation concerns.
- Advocate for policy reforms to allow decentralized waste management.

The real case ending

Robert chose to move forward by fostering dialogue and negotiation rather than confrontation. He recognized that building bridges between the different actors was the only sustainable way forward. For this, he drew inspiration from a People-to-People Dialogue (PPD) Approach, focusing on dialogue, co-creation, and inclusive governance.

The PPD Approach was not a formal strategy within municipal policy but rather an informal, community-driven method of engaging diverse stakeholders in co-production. It involved creating safe spaces for dialogue where local communities, municipal authorities, and private actors could meet face-to-face, share their concerns, and jointly explore solutions. While focusing on the issue of composting and waste governance, it also meant to advance the culture of participation and show a way to make community participation a more integral part of municipal governance. Robert and his team carried out the PPD Approach in three main phases:

Phase 1: Community mobilization and active listening.

Robert began by organizing open community meetings and informal gatherings, inviting both residents and representatives of small businesses. To strengthen the credibility of their claims and ensure systematic input, they collaborated with a local university to design and conduct a survey. The university's involvement was voluntary and based on student and faculty interest in community-based sustainability work, as no additional resources were available. The survey gathered data on how community members were managing their organic waste and their willingness to formalize these practices. This helped to build a strong case backed by community voices and evidence.

Phase 2: Multi-stakeholder dialogue and negotiation.

Once they had community support and data, Robert and key volunteers reached out to municipal authorities and private waste contractors. They organized a series of dialogue forums, sometimes facilitated by neutral academic partners, where all stakeholders could express their interests and concerns. Importantly, the conversations were framed around shared goals: reducing landfill waste, improving local sustainability, and fostering community engagement. The municipal government, while initially hesitant, demonstrated openness and a willingness to engage once they saw the community's seriousness and commitment to responsible composting. These dialogues laid the groundwork for identifying areas of compromise and cooperation.

Phase 3: Pilot project and institutionalization

The dialogues resulted in the creation of a Sustainability Task Force composed of municipal officials, private waste managers, community representatives, and academic experts. Participation in the Task Force was voluntary and done alongside the participants' regular professional and personal responsibilities. Together, they co-designed a pilot project to test a hybrid composting model that integrated small-scale, community-led initiatives with the centralized waste system. A clear regulatory framework was developed to ensure sanitation and public health standards.

Additionally, a Strategic Project Oversight Panel (SPOP) was established to monitor and evaluate the project's progress. This panel included local community members, municipal staff, and researchers, all engaging on a voluntary basis. The panel's work included regular monitoring meetings, compiling feedback from local composting sites, and advising the municipality on necessary adjustments. One of the key outcomes was the municipality's decision to amend local waste regulations to allow for properly managed decentralized composting initiatives.

The Remaining Challenges

Following the successful pilot project, Robert and the stakeholders faced new challenges in scaling up and institutionalizing the composting initiative. Expanding beyond pilot areas required addressing uneven levels of interest and capacity across neighborhoods, ensuring stable funding mechanisms, and formalizing responsibilities without overburdening community members who participated voluntarily.

The municipality, recognizing the value of the pilot, began integrating community composting into its long-term waste strategy. However, this required continuous negotiation with private contractors to redefine contractual arrangements, and developing training and support programs for new community composting sites.

Furthermore, ensuring political commitment over time was a persistent challenge, particularly as elected officials change and priorities shift. This reflects a common reality in local democratic innovation: transformative efforts often rely on voluntary engagement and informal governance arrangements, raising questions about sustainability and equity in the long run. The community actors, municipal staff, and academic partners therefore worked to embed the composting model within broader sustainability policies and urban planning frameworks, aiming to make it a permanent feature of the city's waste system.

Final discussion questions:

Step out of Robert's shoes and consider the broader lessons and wider applications from the Monteverde example.

- What risks and trade-offs should local governments be aware of when opening up decision-making to community-led initiatives?
- How would different management costs and municipal taxes affect this scenario? How can carbon balance be weighed in?
- Can the strategies used in Monteverde be applied to other sustainability challenges, such as renewable energy or water management? What would need to be adapted?
- What tools can be used to assess the (economic, ecological, and social) benefits of community-based Nature-Based Solutions (NBS)?

Youth Engagement in Forestry in Upper Allgäu¹, Germany

How can youth engagement be deepened in rural nature-based solutions? This case follows a forester's efforts to move beyond curriculum-based forest education and foster long-term youth involvement in sustainable forestry through facilitating co-creation, partnerships, and hands-on experiences.

Authors: Clara Orstadius², Gerd Lupp³, Reviewer: Fabio Montagnino⁴

Learning cases are structured real-world dilemmas that provide government officials with tools and reflections to navigate similar challenges, fostering critical thinking and practical problem-solving.

By reading and discussing this case, participants will:

- Understand how hands-on experiences and social incentives can foster long-term stewardship.
- Reflect on strategies to move from awareness-raising to active youth leadership.
- Identify ways to create partnerships that support inclusive and motivating youth programs.

The setting

In Upper Allgäu, a region with vast forested landscapes and a strong tradition of land stewardship, engaging young people in sustainable forestry and Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) is recognized as important but it remains a persistent challenge.

While in the region of Bavaria, in Germany, education policies foresee some level of forest education for children, these programs are often limited to single school visits with

¹ [Upper Allgäu is an Assessment Case](#) in the TRANS-lighthouses project

² International Centre for Local Democracy

³ Technical University Munich

⁴ Cyprus Institute

minimal long-term impact. Many young people do not see forests or conservation as relevant to their daily lives, and reflecting about nature and forests rarely extends beyond what is required in school curricula. Even in this very rural area, fewer and fewer children grow up with direct nature experiences, and have little connection to nature.

At the same time, climate change is severely affecting local forests, requiring a new generation of land stewards to take an active role in protecting and managing them. Without effective strategies to foster genuine youth interest, there is a risk that efforts to engage in protecting and taking care of nature will drop, and there will be a lack of skilled individuals needed to sustain them.

This learning case from the Upper Allgäu explores how one forester sought to bridge this gap by moving beyond formal education mandates to actively inspire young people to see themselves as part of nature and its future caretakers.

The challenge

Silvanus Berger has spent years running educational programs for children in Bavarian schools, introducing them to sustainable forestry. However, he recognizes that while these programs create awareness, they rarely lead to long-term involvement.

With climate change threatening the region's forests, Silvanus wants to ensure that today's youth see themselves as active stewards of the land, not just visitors to nature. He knows that future protection of the forest depends on this. His vision is to move beyond school-based awareness programs and create pathways for deeper youth engagement that foster long-term responsibility and connection to nature. How can Silvanus engage young persons in forest stewardship beyond the single contacts in formal school curricula, and motivate them to actively participate in NBS on their own initiative?

To his advantage, he has access to a learning space, a vast forest, and the support of the relevant administrative bodies to work more with youth. But he faces obstacles:

- Lack of time and interest: Many existing programs have only little contact to nature. Many children and teenagers are more drawn to digital entertainment, sports, or urban activities than to spending time outdoors.
- Resource limitations: The forestry department and schools have limited capacity and resources for educational activities and already struggle to cover them.

Nonetheless, Silvanus develops a strategy to overcome these barriers. He wants to use hands-on activities, and partnerships with local businesses to make the activities, engagement and participation meaningful and rewarding for young people, but needs help.

Discussion questions - round 1

- How can Silvanus fill the suggested government educational activities with life and make it meaningful for young people?
- What type of businesses can he leverage to help make engagement attractive and meaningful for older children and adolescents?
- What other stakeholders can Silvanus involve to leverage resources and how can he convince them that youth involvement in nature and raising awareness for nature needs creates long-term value?

Pretend you are in Silvanus' shoes, and help him design a programme that moves beyond a one-time educational activity foreseen in education plans to create awareness, develop and support the development of a sense taking care for nature and sustained engagement.

Images from a 4-minute explainer video on children, youth and nature-based solution, telling the story of Upper Allgäu. Artwork: Magic Markers

The solution

To address these challenges, over the years, Silvanus developed a set of multi-tiered programmes, combining formal education filling in close dialogue with the schools, but also enriching the formal education plans with life, social incentives, and direct experience:

- He provides hands-on activities with students, allowing them to shape activities and combining them learning also social competencies.
- He partnered with local businesses that process products from the forest but also others interested in supporting youth leadership. The partnerships offered youth opportunities to make their engagement valuable for future careers and life including strengthening “soft skills” such as cooperation, working together and tackling challenges.
- Reflecting the ideas of “multifunctional forestry”, integrating economic, ecological and social aspects, his work with community-driven activity, organizing youth-led activities and providing networking opportunities strengthen all dimensions and is an interesting example for NBS projects.

Recognizing the gap between formal educational goals, their often flimsy implementation and creating real meaningful youth engagement, Silvanus Berger knew that true environmental stewardship required more than passive learning—it needed a sense of ownership and creating a personal connection.

He redesigned youth engagement in forestry, focusing on three key areas: co-creation, partnerships, and social incentives. Instead of simply guiding students through pre-planned activities, he gave them a say in designing their activities and projects. Working with teenagers, he encouraged them to identify environmental challenges they cared about. By giving them real hands-on cases to work with, Silvanus found that participation became more meaningful, and students became more invested in the outcomes.

Perhaps the most transformative aspect of his approach was reframing forestry work as a social and developmental experience. Rather than positioning forests or nature conservation as a task or duty, Silvanus organized activities that emphasized teamwork, leadership, and adventure. He partnered with local businesses and organizations also beyond the forest sector. The idea was to create awareness and to combine topics advocating for forests with social skills, like practicing working in teams. Having businesses and enterprises as partners helped encourage young participants that engaging with and working in the forest is valued beyond school credits. This collaboration helped to better anchor the importance of taking care for nature, and to encourage sceptical stakeholders to get active as well. Silvanus introduced hands-on experiences like overnight forest camps, peer-led restoration projects, and storytelling initiatives where youth could share their work. As a result, young people began to associate forest engagement not just with responsibility, but with personal growth, friendships, and fun.

Over time, this multi-layered strategy produced tangible results. The number of students voluntarily continuing forest-related activities beyond school programs increased, and some young participants took on leadership roles, mentoring younger students or advocating for sustainable land management in their communities. The program also gained recognition among policymakers, leading to increased institutional support for youth involvement.

While challenges remained, such as the need for continued funding and ensuring long-term participation, there was a clear shift where a top-down obligation had evolved into a bottom-up movement. Young people were becoming active contributors to the future of Upper Allgäu's natural treasures.

Final discussion questions:

- How can planners balance the urgency of finding solutions with the time that is necessary to engage in co-diagnostics?
- How can local governments balance technical expertise (for example their understanding of biodiversity) with community knowledge and other areas of interest) in decision-making for NBS?
- What are the risks of failing to engage local stakeholders in environmental governance projects?
- What are similar challenges you experience in your own work with NBS?

Revitalizing Community Engagement through Cultural Heritage in the Troodos Mountains¹

How can cultural heritage and emotional ties to a place revitalize stalled participation in the co-governance of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS)? Set in the terraced landscapes of the Troodos Mountains, Cyprus, this case follows a landscape planner's effort to shift from technical restoration to culturally grounded engagement. It invites reflection on how local identity, traditional knowledge, and informal networks can support inclusive environmental governance, especially in rural areas where formal participation is weak but attachment to land remains strong.

Authors: Clara Orstadius², Georgios Artopoulos³, Reviewer: Ana Maria Vargas⁴

Learning cases are structured real-world dilemmas that provide government officials with tools and reflections to navigate similar challenges, fostering critical thinking and practical problem-solving.

Learning objectives

- Understand how cultural framing and emotional attachment to place can support participatory governance in NBS.
- Explore how traditional knowledge holders and informal networks can strengthen stalled community engagement efforts.
- Reflect on how participatory methods can be adapted to rural contexts with low formal engagement.
- Identify transferable strategies for aligning ecological restoration with social and cultural meaning.
- Recognize how cultural engagement can help spark youth interest in nature-based practices, even in regions where land connection has declined.

¹ [Troodos is an assessment case](#) in the TRANS-lighthouses project.

² International Centre for Local Democracy

³ Cyprus Institute

⁴ Lund University, International Centre for Local Democracy

Introduction: the terraces of Troodos

The terraced landscapes of the Troodos Mountains in Cyprus have shaped both the ecology and identity of the region for centuries. Built by hand with dry-stone walls, these terraces were once central to agricultural life and community well-being. Today, they are recognized as a form of Nature-Based Solution (NBS), preventing erosion, regulating water, supporting biodiversity, and maintaining the stability of steep hillsides.

Yet, over recent decades, depopulation and land abandonment have led to widespread deterioration of the terraces. While many villagers express pride in the landscape and care deeply about its condition, there is a widespread perception that its restoration is someone else's responsibility - whether that be the state, NGOs, or technical experts. In a context where the culture of participatory governance is generally low, engaging citizens in shared landscape management is particularly difficult.

Environmental NGOs, researchers, and the municipality initiated a pilot to restore select terrace systems, with the dual goals of ecological benefit and community co-ownership. However, early participatory efforts, such as meetings and workshops, did not yield the hoped-for engagement. Though the environmental problem was acknowledged, it remained distant from everyday concerns.

Challenge: why nobody came despite caring

Christina, a landscape planner and community facilitator employed by a research institute, led the participatory component of the project. Despite a technically well-prepared plan and institutional backing, participation from residents remained limited. Many locals appreciated the restoration effort, but assumed it should be handled by formal authorities or external actors.

It became clear that the project's framing - it was presented a technical solution to erosion and climate threats - failed to resonate on a personal level. At one community meeting, an elderly villager challenged Christina:

"You speak of soil and rainfall, but these terraces are about how we lived, worked, and fed our children."

The social fabric of the community revealed a complex mix of actors with differing levels of connection and influence. Elderly residents, many of whom held traditional knowledge in dry-stone walling, were proud of their heritage but felt overlooked during initial consultations. Their skills had not been sought out in a meaningful way, and many assumed their input was no longer relevant. Most young people have moved from the region to study and work in urban areas or abroad, and the absence and disconnect of youth was notable in the area. Meanwhile, the young families who did remain were somewhat disconnected from the land. Most had grown up without a strong link to the terraced landscapes and were unaware of the cultural or ecological value these structures held. Their priorities often lay elsewhere, and they had not been actively included in the project's outreach.

Expatriates - people originally from the area who now lived elsewhere - sometimes retained strong emotional ties and returned during holidays or religious festivals. While not consistently present, they held informal influence in their home communities and often owned land that could be part of restoration efforts. However, they were difficult to reach through standard participation methods. Local institutions such as church networks and cultural associations still carried significant social legitimacy, yet they had not been mobilized during early engagement.

At the institutional level, NGOs and researchers were focused on ecosystem services, climate adaptation, and the long-term environmental goals of the restoration. Their language and methods often felt distant from daily village life. Municipal and district officials, on the other hand, were primarily concerned with securing project funding, approving land-use strategies, and ensuring policy compliance. While these roles are essential, they did not support the depth of local interaction that was needed.

The elderly man had revealed the disconnect for Christina. People cared for the land, but not necessarily about how they were being asked to participate. Christina realized that unless the project tapped into the deep cultural meanings embedded in the landscape, and addressed people's sense of ownership and identity, it would struggle to build lasting local involvement.

Christina faced a dilemma: how could she foster meaningful community participation in landscape restoration when technical language and external facilitation failed to resonate?

Discussion: help Christina make a plan

- How can Christina and her team reframe the project to resonate with the lived experience and identity of the community?
- What role can traditional knowledge holders — such as elders and craftspeople — play in reenergizing a stalled participatory process?
- How could different stakeholder groups (e.g. youth, expatriates, NGOs) be brought into the process in ways that speak to their values and experiences?

Stakeholders involved

Elderly residents	Holders of traditional knowledge (e.g. dry-stone walling), some of whom felt overlooked in earlier consultations.
Local councils and church networks	Important gatekeepers of legitimacy and community trust.
Expatriates	People who had left but still owned land and returned for festivals; often absent in meetings, but emotionally invested.
Youth and young families	Largely disconnected from land-based practices, often unaware of the terraces' purpose or history.
NGOs and researchers	Focused on ecosystem services, climate adaptation, and long-term restoration goals.
Municipal and district officials	Needed to approve land-use strategies and manage funding streams.

Model of co-production of eco-system services

Infographic from Christos Zoumides, Adriana Bruggeman, Hakan Djuma, Revitalising terraced landscapes: Co-production of ecosystem services for sustainable futures, *Geography and Sustainability*, 2025,100306,ISSN 2666-6839, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geosus.2025.100306>.

Real case ending: tapping into tradition and cultural heritage

Faced with declining participation in early outreach efforts, Christina and the project team adjusted their approach. Rather than continuing with standard stakeholder consultations, they began working through trusted local institutions—such as the municipal council, cultural associations, and church networks—to identify and mobilize people with strong emotional ties to the landscape.

This included elders with traditional knowledge of dry-stone terrace construction and part-time residents who returned for festivals or seasonal work. This process evolved into what came to be known informally as the Terrace Apprenticeship and Co-Action Program, a model that paired traditional knowledge holders with residents and volunteers in a format that emphasized mutual learning and shared responsibility.

The team initiated small, hands-on restoration workshops in select communities, not as technical training events but as cultural gatherings. These sessions integrated traditional food, music, and storytelling, and invited local knowledge holders to teach their skills. Framing the events as acts of cultural preservation rather than environmental restoration made them more inviting. Participants described the workshops as "reconnecting with the land" and "rebuilding pride."

Participation increased steadily. Expatriates visiting during festivals joined and shared family histories linked to the land. Younger participants, initially unfamiliar with the terraces, began to see their value as part of local identity. Stories emerged about how the terraces had supported families during difficult times. This meant they were reviving not only techniques, but family histories and a sense of intergenerational continuity. Restoration became personal. Residents noted that the process felt more inclusive and trust-building than previous top-down efforts.

The project built momentum and the model was scaled and replicated for use in other villages. NGOs used it in post-fire erosion prevention, and municipalities began including terrace rehabilitation in broader climate adaptation and resilience strategies. A solid outcome was the perceived need to continue this model. That means the project had gained social acceptance in the community while the scientific partners saw the progress with regards to erosion and water management.

Building on this momentum, the team explored ways to maintain engagement with remote landowners and diaspora members throughout the year, including informal channels like community WhatsApp groups and email updates tied to seasonal restoration activities. While sustaining engagement and attracting youth remains an ongoing effort, the case demonstrated that reconnecting environmental objectives with cultural heritage can activate participation even in areas with low formal participatory culture.

Discussion questions: lessons learned and knowledge transfer

Now exit the Troodos mountains and consider your own context, and NBS existing around you.

- What lessons from Troodos could be applied to other NBS projects involving landscape restoration or rural participation?
- What are the risks or drawbacks of using cultural heritage as an entry point for ecological engagement? Does it create conflicting values?
- What informal or cultural networks in your own context could be activated to support NBS planning or implementation?

Key messages

- Technically sound restoration projects may fail if they lack cultural resonance.
- Participation improves when environmental action is linked to identity, memory, and shared heritage.
- Trusted local actors and informal institutions are critical entry points for engagement in regions with low participation.
- Restoring landscapes can also restore community cohesion when approached holistically.
- Small-scale, culturally grounded pilot actions can be powerful starting points for long-term participation.
- Sustained participation in rural NBS initiatives benefits from three interconnected principles: inclusivity (involving all groups meaningfully), consistency (maintaining presence and follow-up), and cultural sensitivity (honoring local rhythms, memory, and identity)

Recreio é Natureza in Barcelos: When Children Co-Design Nature-Based Schoolyards

How can children meaningfully shape Nature-Based Solutions? This case follows a Portuguese school that invited students to redesign their schoolyard while learning to navigate budget limits, safety standards, and democratic decision-making.

Authors: Clara Orstadius¹, Andreia Coelho²

Learning cases are structured real-world dilemmas that provide government officials with tools and reflections to navigate similar challenges, fostering critical thinking and practical problem-solving.

By reading and discussing this case, participants will:

- Understand how schoolyards can become entry points for Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) and democratic learning.
- Explore what happens when child-led co-creation meets municipal regulations, safety standards, and procurement systems.
- Reflect on the role of schools as spaces not only for learning about nature, but for governing with nature.

Introduction

In Barcelos, a municipality in northern Portugal, school playgrounds are usually designed in familiar ways: asphalt surfaces, fixed metal structures, and clear divisions between learning indoors and playing outdoors.

¹ International Centre for Local Democracy

² Barcelos Municipality, Division for Education

All images are credited to Barcelos Municipality.

But research shows that green spaces increase well-being and inspires other types of learning. Also, the climate crisis calls for rebuilding an understanding and respect for nature. In recent years, municipal leaders and educators began asking a different question:

What if the schoolyard could become a place where children reconnect with nature, build climate resilience, and shape their own environment?

Through the TRANS-lighthouses project, Barcelos launched a pilot called "Recreio é Natureza" ("Playtime is Nature"), aiming to transform school outdoor spaces into nature-based learning environments. The pilot was implemented in three schools, including *Escola Básica 2,3 Abel Varzim*, where students from the 5th to the 9th grade levels would take part in redesigning their own playground.

The project was ambitious: not only to introduce greener infrastructure, but to experiment with participatory governance where children become co-creators of spaces they use.

The promise of participation and greening at the Abel Varzim school

At EB 2,3 Abel Varzim, the schoolyard was large and spacious, but heavily paved with asphalt. Vast open areas were fully exposed to the sun, with very few trees or shaded spaces. During warmer days, the heat radiating from the asphalt made the playground even hotter, discouraging students from using many parts of the space. Although the school had ample room, much of it remained underused due to the lack of natural elements, shade, and comfortable areas for diverse and inclusive play.

Catarina was a teacher and sustainability coordinator at EB 2,3 Abel Varzim. Along with her peers, she noticed growing challenges:

- Students spent less time in nature than previous generations
- Outdoor spaces were not designed for diverse needs
- With climate change, the summers had grown hotter and there was less shade
- The schoolyard felt like an "in-between space," not part of learning

She discussed with the municipality, and developed a deep belief in the project's vision of a participatory process where green spaces are collaboratively designed. She thought having their own ideas realised and taken seriously will equip the children to understand their role in creating the life and society that is good for them, and build lifelong skills.

When the municipality introduced the pilot, excitement grew quickly. It was important the children, their teachers and parents, and the school and municipal leadership bought into the benefits. They planned to conduct workshops on Nature-Based Solutions and climate adaptation, participatory methods and budgeting, and on play, creativity, and risk in outdoor learning.

A few weeks into the planning, Catarina sat in a meeting with the municipal team. On the table lay the school's maps, preliminary sketches of the playground, and a document outlining the allocated budget. The project was real. The funding was secured. The transformation would lead to actual construction.

The message from the municipality was polite, but clear: This is a public investment. It must comply with safety regulations. It must stay within budget. It must meet accessibility standards. It must be maintainable over time.

Catarina returned to her classroom and looked out toward the playground. She knew their ideas would be bold, and could hear their excitement:

At the same time, she understood the responsibility resting with the municipality.

If a child were injured...

If the budget was exceeded...

If maintenance was not guaranteed...

The entire pilot could stall. Catarina realized that the real challenge was not managing rejection later, but designing the process from the start.

How could students dream freely — and still understand that public space comes with rules?

What does "meaningful participation" require when final decisions depend on regulations and experts? How can they avoid being set up for disappointment? How could imagination and accountability grow together, rather than collide?

So her **dilemma** becomes:

How can she structure a process where children work *with* the real constraints — budget, safety, maintenance, accessibility — without killing creativity and ownership?

→ Help Caterina design a participatory process.

- How do you ensure that budget and safety constraints are built into the ideas from the beginning?
- Who can you engage?
- How should the selection process be, between all the ideas, in a way that is fair and teaches children about democracy?

Stop here to reflect and discuss your strategy, before proceeding to the read case ending. To your help, consider the stakeholders.

Stakeholders Involved

- Students: Co-designers of the playground, seeking ownership and recognition
- Teachers and school leadership: Facilitators balancing pedagogy, inclusion, and feasibility
- Municipal education department: Champions of innovation and community engagement
- Technical services and engineers: Responsible for safety, procurement, compliance
- Parents and local community: Supporters, but also concerned about risk and fairness
- TRANS-lighthouses partners: Providing frameworks for co-creation and scaling

Image: Session with parents

The real process at EB 2,3 Abel Varzim

Before students entered the process, meetings were held with teachers, school leadership, and technical staff. These sessions clarified the goals of *Recreio é Natureza* and the scope of the project. The budget framework was presented. Safety and accessibility standards were discussed openly, including the risks parents perceived about playing in nature, and the counterarguments of the long-term missed opportunities of not developing the motor skills, serenity and system thinking that come from interacting with nature.

This helped avoid misunderstandings later. Teachers understood that the process would require time and integration into class schedules, and parents understood that this was a structured transformation with clear limits.

As a starting point, students were introduced to an inspiring local example: the Escola Secundária de Barcelos and its Arboretum, a living space that has existed for over 40 years. Known as a successful assessment case, the Arboretum demonstrates how nature can be meaningfully integrated within a school environment over time. Seeing that such a space had been sustained for decades helped students understand that bringing nature into school grounds is not an abstract idea, but a realistic and achievable transformation.

When the student workshops began, the first task was simple: walk the yard. Catarina watched students come alive in the process. They mapped the schoolyard, identified challenges, and dreamed aloud: "We want places to rest under trees." "We want outdoor classes." "Why is nature always outside the school walls?" Students moved through the space in groups, looking at it with new eyes. Where do younger children usually play? Where do older students gather? Which areas are always in the sun? Where do conflicts happen? Where does nothing happen at all? They marked their observations on printed maps. The yard began to look less like one large playground and more like a set of different zones with different possibilities.

After the presentation of the proposals by the various classes, a collaborative process of joint construction was chosen, integrating the different contributions into a common final proposal, representative

of the ideas and needs of all.

In the next sessions, the idea of Nature-Based Solutions was introduced — not in abstract terms, but through questions. What would create shade here? What kind of vegetation could grow along this slope? How can surfaces stay cooler in summer? How to have a pond at school? Facilitators related this to biodiversity, climate control, and inclusivity. Students discussed trees, planting beds, seating areas, and how nature could become part of everyday school life rather than something outside the gates.

Then the design work began. Working in groups, students developed proposals for different parts of the yard. Landscape architects joined the sessions, sitting down at the tables rather than lecturing at the front. When a group suggested a structure, the architects asked: Where would it be attached? How much space does it need around it? What happens when it rains? Does it need to be cleaned?

The conversations did not close ideas down but help reshape them and piece a puzzle together.

Digital tools were used to visualize the proposals. Students worked with digital models of the schoolyard, placing elements into the space and testing how they fit together. Seeing their ideas appear on screen made the process feel immediate and concrete. They could move a structure, add a tree, adjust a path, and instantly see the effect.

As the first designs were developed, the budget discussion entered the room more clearly. Facilitators explained that the project had a fixed financial framework. Some elements require more investment than others. Large constructions affect what remains for planting. Ground preparation affects what can be built on top, and so on. Students began to ask different questions. “If we choose this, what do we have to remove?” “Is this more expensive than planting trees?” The conversation shifted from “What do we want?” to “What should we prioritize?”

Groups revised their proposals. Some ideas were scaled down. Others were combined. In a few cases, elements were moved to different zones to make better use of space. The adjustments were made openly, in dialogue with the architects and teachers.

Catarina noticed something as the workshops progressed. When constraints were explained clearly and early, they did not reduce enthusiasm but merely changed its tone. The students were not only imagining a new playground. They were learning how decisions are made.

Next, a process inspired by the principles of participatory budgeting began. There were lively debates, moments of argumentation, comments, and self-organization on the part of the students.

Each class presented its proposal and chose the aspects it considered priorities. However, instead of proceeding to a final vote that would select only one project, a collaborative process of integrating the different ideas was chosen.

The classes' proposals were presented to the school community, allowing for the sharing of arguments, priorities, and justifications. From this dialogue, a common final proposal was built, which incorporated the contributions of the various classes and sought to reflect the wishes of the student body as a whole.

Image: Proposal analysis with TRANS-lighthouses scholar

The winning proposal

The winning proposal, as agreed by the students, prioritized the creation of integrated living spaces with natural elements, promoting encounters, well-being, and the diversified use of recess. Increasing shaded areas became a priority, recognizing the need to make the space more comfortable and usable throughout the school year.

One of the structuring decisions was the removal of part of the asphalt, replacing it with more natural and permeable solutions, contributing to the reduction of heat and the environmental improvement of the space.

Among the central elements of the proposal, the following stood out:

- The creation of a pond, as a pedagogical space and promoter of biodiversity;
- An open-air amphitheater, designed for academic activities, presentations, and moments of sharing;
- The creation of spaces for informal interaction and practice, promoting encounters, sharing, and spontaneous dynamics among students.
- A pollinator garden, valuing environmental education and the presence of native species.

The vegetation was conceived not only as a decorative element but also as an organizing structure for the space, creating areas for lingering, shade, and diverse uses.

PROJETOS VENCEDORES: EB 2,3 Abel Varzim

Before implementation, the proposal underwent technical adjustments to ensure safety, accessibility, and sustainable maintenance in the long term. Even so, its central logic—more nature, more shade, less waterproofing, and more spaces for interaction—remained the guiding principle of the transformation.

With a view to maintaining the newly created spaces and ensuring the long-term sustainability of the interventions, as well as continuing the project through new ideas and solutions, the school established the Playground is Nature Club. The club is now permanent and composed of students who voluntarily choose to join, together with a committed group of teachers. In addition to developing new ideas and solutions, members actively participate in the ongoing care and maintenance of the space, strengthening their sense of responsibility and belonging.

Conclusion

For the municipality, the pilot required coordination across departments and a willingness to integrate participatory input into technical systems. For the school, it demonstrated that students can engage seriously with trade-offs and shared responsibility when constraints are transparent.

Recreio é Natureza shows that children can take part in shaping Nature-Based Solutions when participation is structured and transparent. They do not need to be shielded from limits to stay engaged. On the contrary, working within limits can strengthen ownership.

The schoolyard design reflects negotiated choices. The process gave students practical insight into how collective decisions are made — and how democracy operates within rules, resources, and responsibility.

Second-round reflection: Transfer to your own context

Step out of Barcelos and think back to your everyday environment.

- Where in your municipality could children, youth, or communities co-govern public space?
- What systems (procurement, safety, bureaucracy) might block participation — even with good intentions?
- How can local governments redesign institutions to match the ambitions of NBS co-creation?